

Spain case study on cybersecurity technology and information transfer

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Abstract

This report presents an in-depth assessment of Spain’s national framework for dual-use cybersecurity technology transfer and information sharing. Using a mixed-method approach, combining desk research with stakeholder interviews, surveys, and a validation workshop, the study examines the effectiveness of Spain’s cybersecurity governance structures, technology transfer mechanisms and information-sharing practices, as well as the national landscape for dual-use cybersecurity technologies deployment, including the identification of best practices.

Keywords

Cybersecurity, cyber threats, hybrid threats, cybersecurity technology transfer, NIS 2 Directive, dual-use technologies

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence.
AMETIC	The National Digital Industry Association of Spain, COcyber partner leading the synergies with existing initiatives, exploitation and sustainability (WP6), and responsible for the National Case Study Report of Spain (WP4).
BACSI	Project led by the Spanish Air and Space Force, aiming to transform air bases into innovative, connected and intelligent ecosystems using advanced technology
CCN	National Cryptologic Centre
CCN-CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team of the National Cryptologic Centre
CCD COE	NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence.
CDTI	Spanish Centre for Technological Development and Innovation
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team, a group of information security experts who identify, analyse and mitigate cybersecurity incidents and threats
CNC	National Cybersecurity Council
CNI	National Intelligence Centre
CNPIC	National Centre for the Protection of Critical Infrastructure

COcyber	Coordination between the Cybersecurity Civilian and Defense Spheres. It is the project to which this report belongs—specifically, it is part of Task 4.1 within Work Package 4.
CSIC	Spanish National Research Council
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
CSN	National Security Council
DEP	Digital Europe Programme, funding instrument of the European Union.
DGAM	General Directorate of Armament and Material
DIANA	Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic under NATO.
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DORA	Digital Operational Resilience Act – EU regulation that entered into force in January 2025 to strengthen the digital operational resilience of the financial sector.
DSN	Department of Homeland Security
EC	The European Commission, the European public authority funding the COcyber project.
ECC	The European Cybersecurity Competence Centre, the funding authority of the COcyber project.
EDA	European Defence Agency

EDF	European Defence Fund
EECTI	Spanish Strategy for Science, Technology and Innovation.
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity.
ENS	National Security Framework
ERA	European Research Area
EU	The European Union (EU) is a political and economic union of 27 European countries, designed to foster economic cooperation, promote peace, and create a single market with free movement of goods, services, and people
FNC	National Cybersecurity Forum
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
INCIBE	Spanish National Cybersecurity Institute
INCIBE-CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team of INCIBE
IoT	Internet of Things
ISACs	Information Sharing and Analysis Centres, non-profit organisations that provide a central resource for gathering information on cyberthreats.
LEAs	Law Enforcement Agencies
MCCE	Joint Cyberspace Command, the military cyber defence organ
MISP	Malware Information Sharing Platform.

NATO	NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organisation) is a military alliance formed in 1949, consisting of 30 member countries from Europe and North America, aimed at ensuring collective defence and security against common threats. It operates under the principle that an attack on one member is an attack on all.
NCC	National Coordination Centre in Spain for the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre
NIS	Network and Information Systems Directive
NIS2	Directive (EU) 2022/2555 (updated Network and Information Systems Directive)
OCC	Cybersecurity Coordination Office
PNC	National Cybersecurity Plan
PPI	Public Procurement of Innovation
R&D	Research and Development
RENIC	Spanish Network of Excellence on Cybersecurity Research
RNS	National SOC Network
SEPE	Spain's Public Employment Service
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SOC	Security Operations Centre
STIC	Security Technologies, used in CCN's certification catalogue

STIX	Structured Threat Information Expression
TAXII	Trusted Automated Exchange of Indicator Information
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TTO	Technology Transfer Offices
W4C	Women4Cyber

Executive summary

This National Case Study Report provides a comprehensive analysis of Spain's cybersecurity and technology transfer ecosystem, addressing key areas such as the evolution of the national cybersecurity regulations and policies, the role of dual-use technologies, and mechanisms for sharing threat intelligence. The primary objectives of the study are to establish the context of dual-use cybersecurity technology transfer within the Spanish landscape, identify the legal and institutional frameworks governing these processes, and assess the barriers that limit Spain's capacity to achieve comprehensive national resilience against evolving cyber threats.

The study follows a mixed-method approach to ensure comprehensive evidence gathering and validation across the national ecosystem. The methodological framework encompassed four key components: an extensive desk research reviewing relevant scientific literature, national cybersecurity strategies, policies, and legal frameworks; a set of semi-structured stakeholder interviews (15 interviews conducted in total) with representatives from government agencies, the private sector, academia, and civil and defence-related organisations; an online survey disseminated to a broader audience; and finally, an experts' validation workshop, seeking national experts to review and confirm the accuracy of the findings and interpretations. This multi-faceted design provides a robust basis for the subsequent analysis and policy recommendations.

The main findings can be summarized in the following points:

- Spain has built a strong cybersecurity governance framework, supported by the National Cybersecurity Strategy (2019) and the National Cybersecurity Plan (2022–2025). This framework has led Spain to a Tier 1 position in international rankings. However, the implementation of this governance has been moderately effective, due to a fragmented regional implementation, the high vulnerability of SMEs, a significant and growing cybersecurity talent gap, and a persistent mistrust between public and private stakeholders.

- Cybersecurity technology transfer is supported by the National Security Framework and major funding instruments such as INCIBE's Public Procurement of Innovation program and CDTI's Misiones, Cervera and Neotec programs. However, technology transfer is constrained by bureaucratic rigidity, unclear intellectual property rights rules in publicly funded R&D projects, and a cultural preference for foreign solutions. Together, these factors limit the adoption and scaling of domestic cybersecurity technologies.
- Spain has developed an information-sharing structure with a dual national CERT system (CCN-CERT and INCIBE-CERT), the National SOC Network, and specialized tools (such as MISP). However, its effectiveness is constrained by mistrust among stakeholders (due to fears of reputational or legal consequences in case of reporting a cyber incident), strict compliance standards (under NIS2 and GDPR), and the lack of a clear national point of reference.
- The absence of a comprehensive national strategy for dual-use technologies limits their deployment, which is constrained by the long export-licensing timelines, restrictive intellectual property rights rules, and the inherent ethical challenges, compromising the national competitiveness in the dual-use cybersecurity technology sector.

Finally, the report identifies a preliminary set of policy recommendations aimed at addressing the identified structural gaps to reinforce Spain's national cyber resilience.

1. Introduction

This section introduces the purpose and scope of the case study, providing context on the importance of cybersecurity technology and information transfer in the national landscape. It outlines the rationale for conducting the study, the key questions it seeks to address, and the methodologies used to gather and analyse data.

This national case study on Spain is one of four national case studies conducted within the scope of the COcyber project, alongside the ones carried out in Hungary, Lithuania and Slovenia. Together, the four country studies provide a diverse sample that enables the findings from individual national reports to be compared at the European level, allowing for a more robust insights and recommendations that can inform EU-wide cybersecurity policies.

1.1 Background and context of cybersecurity technology and information transfer

The current complex and uncertain geopolitical landscape, combined with the progressive digital transition, has led to an increase of both the sophistication and the frequency of cybersecurity incidents. According to the National Cybersecurity Institute (INCIBE), the number of cybersecurity incidents has increased by 16.6% in 2025, following previous high-impact cases such as the 2021 cyberattack on Spain's State Public Employment Service (SEPE). This evolution has elevated cybersecurity to a strategic national security priority for Spain, highlighting the need for robust national capabilities and resilience plans in this domain.

Spain elaborated a National Cybersecurity Strategy in 2019. The Strategy objectives range from capacity building and enhancing national resilience to the development of the national cybersecurity industry and talent. The Spanish regulatory framework is aligned with the European Union legislation, including the transposition of the NIS Directive (2016) in 2018 and the ongoing process to transpose the NIS22 Directive (2022) into the Spanish legislative framework.

In this context, effective technology transfer is a crucial element to reinforce the cybersecurity resilience of Spain, supporting both the national security and the competitiveness of the national cybersecurity industry. Ensuring the scalability and market deployment of domestic cybersecurity solutions would reduce the actual dependency of Spain on non-European cybersecurity technologies. In fact, this would contribute to the broader EU-objective to strengthen of the European strategic autonomy.

The inherent dual-use nature of most cybersecurity technologies provides an additional strategic layer to the sector at both the national and the European-level, reinforcing even more the importance of mitigating technological dependencies on third countries. Furthermore, information sharing remains as the other central element to reinforce both national and international resilience against cyber threats. Information sharing practices include exchange of threat intelligence, incident reporting, and close and continuous coordination among national and European-level Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs).

The rationale for conducting this study is based on the necessity to conduct more in-depth research regarding the mechanisms through which domestic cybersecurity technologies are transferred to the market and how information sharing is facilitated across sectors in Spain, given the central role these processes play in fostering the national cybersecurity capabilities and resilience.

1.2 Objectives of the case study

The primary objective of the COcyber national case study is to analyse the state of cybersecurity technology transfer and information-sharing mechanisms in Spain. Aligned with the broader goals of the COcyber project, the report specifically aims to:

- Provide a comprehensive overview of national policies, strategies, key stakeholders, and current challenges and gaps within the Spanish cybersecurity ecosystem.

- Analyse the Spanish technology transfer framework, from the relevant legal and regulatory frameworks to the main responsible institutions, as well as to document incentives and barriers affecting the effectiveness of the process.
- Assess the existing information sharing mechanisms in Spain, identifying national policies and frameworks, threat intelligence-sharing tools and the principal challenges in cross-sectoral information sharing.
- Examine the strategic role of dual-use technologies in the national context, reviewing the governance framework, listing the main challenges related to their regulation and management, and identifying best practices and success cases.
- Propose policy recommendations to strengthen the Spanish cybersecurity resilience based on the identified gaps.

1.3 Scope and limitations

This case study analyses the frameworks and mechanisms for cybersecurity technology transfer and information sharing in Spain. It covers exiting policies, legal frameworks and best practices, and explores the roles of the main national-level stakeholders, including government bodies and regulators, private sector organisations, research and academic institutions and non-for-profit organisations.

The report adopts a mixed-method approach combining desk research, semi-structured in-depth interviews to key national stakeholders, an online survey to gather additional information, and a final validation workshop to refine the main findings.

This case study presents two main limitations:

- **Scope of data and information:** The study relies on publicly available information and data, obtained through the research methodologies previously listed. It does not cover classified or sensitive information that is not accessible through open sources or voluntary disclosure.

- **Dynamism of the cybersecurity sector:** The findings represent the present state of the cybersecurity sector in November 2025 and may not fully account for the fast-evolving cybersecurity threat and technology landscape.

2. Methodology

The Spain's national case study follows a mixed-method approach combining desk research, semi-structured interviews, an online survey, and a national expert validation workshop.

2.1 Research methods

This section outlines the methodological framework employed in the COcyber national case studies to investigate cybersecurity technology transfer and information-sharing mechanisms in Spain. A mixed-methods approach was adopted to ensure a comprehensive understanding of each country's cybersecurity landscape, facilitating both depth and breadth in data collection and analysis.

The research design encompasses four key components:

- **Desk research:** An extensive review of national cybersecurity strategies, policies, legal frameworks, and academic literature was conducted to establish a foundational understanding of Spain's cybersecurity environment.
- **Semi-structured interviews:** Targeted interviews with key stakeholders—including representatives from government agencies, private sector entities, academic institutions, and civil society organisations—were carried out to gather in-depth qualitative insights.
- **Online survey:** A structured survey was disseminated to a broader group of stakeholders to collect quantitative data and validate findings from the interviews and desk research.
- **National validation workshop:** AMETIC hosted a workshop to review preliminary findings, ensuring the accuracy and relevance of the data and interpretations.

This multi-faceted methodology was designed to capture a holistic view of cybersecurity practices and challenges in each nation, providing a robust basis for comparative analysis and policy recommendations.

2.1.1. Desk research

A preliminary literature review and policy analysis has been conducted at the national level. This phase includes the review of:

- National cybersecurity strategies and policies
- Legal and regulatory frameworks
- Existing technology transfer and information-sharing mechanisms
- Relevant academic and industry publications

2.1.2. Semi-structured stakeholder interviews

Using a common interview guide, a series of in-depth interviews will be carried out with national stakeholders. Stakeholder categories included:

- Government agencies and regulators;
- Private sector representatives (including critical infrastructure operators);
- Research and academic institutions;
- Civil society or industry associations;
- Defence-related organisations.

A total of 15 interviews have been conducted, with three stakeholders interviewed per category. A detailed list of stakeholders is provided in Annex 4.

2.1.3. Online stakeholder survey

An online survey has been distributed to a broader set of mapped stakeholders in each country. This survey aimed to:

- Reach a wider audience beyond direct interviews;

- Validate preliminary findings;
- Collect additional quantitative or qualitative insights.

Through the survey, Spain has received 10 additional inputs from national experts and stakeholders.

2.1.4. National experts' validation workshop

A national validation workshop with cybersecurity and technology transfer experts was organised on November 21, 2025.

The objectives were:

- To present and validate the draft findings
- To gather final inputs and ensure stakeholder alignment
- To refine recommendations based on multi-sectoral expert feedback

2.2 Data analysis and reporting

Data gathered through desk research, interviews, and the online survey has been analysed thematically and synthesised into draft case study reports. The findings have been validated through the national workshops before finalising the deliverables.

3. National cybersecurity landscape

This section analyses the current cybersecurity framework and key stakeholders in Spain. It also identifies the main challenges of this governance structure.

3.1 Overview of national cybersecurity policies and strategies

Early developments (2013–2017)

Spain's approach to cybersecurity significantly evolved during the 2010's decade. Prior to 2013, the country lacked a unified national framework, and responsibilities were dispersed

across several institutions, the main ones being the National Intelligence Centre (CNI), the Ministry of the Interior, and the Ministry of Defence. As the digital transition of the country progressed, cybersecurity incidents became more frequent and sophisticated, creating a need for a comprehensive national cybersecurity scheme to coordinate the national ecosystem and strengthen the country's resilience in front of the new threats.

In this context, in 2013, Spain adopted its first National Cybersecurity Strategy, the first official cybersecurity roadmap in Spain. It became the first specific document exclusively dedicated to cybersecurity and its governance model in the national context.

In parallel, another key development in 2013 was the creation of the National Cybersecurity Council. It was established by agreement of the National Security Council, a delegated commission of the Spanish Government created also in 2013 and chaired by the Spanish President. The National Security Council decided to launch specialized committees in key areas, and the cybersecurity was among the first to be created, which highlights its importance within the broader framework of national security.

Two notable milestones were achieved in the following years. First, in 2015, the adoption of the National Security Law (Law 36/2015) created the foundational framework for the governance of cybersecurity and the protection of critical infrastructure. Later, in 2017, the National Security Strategy identified cybersecurity as a strategic national security priority for Spain, giving it a central role within the broader national security framework.

Integration with the European Framework (2016–2018)

Spanish regulatory framework in cybersecurity is deeply interconnected with the regulatory initiatives promoted from the European Union (EU). In July 2016, the EU adopted the NIS Directive, with the objective to improve national cybersecurity capabilities across the EU and enhance cybersecurity resilience and build cooperation at the EU level. The same 2016 Spain started the analytical work to transpose the directive. The National Cybersecurity Council assumed a pivotal role as the political and technical coordinator.

Two years later, the formal transposition of the NIS Directive in the Spanish legal system was framed through the Royal Decree-Law 12/2018 of September 7, on the Security of Network and Information Systems.

National Cybersecurity Strategy (2019)

Currently, Spain's cybersecurity policy is primarily articulated through the 2019 National Cybersecurity Strategy, which was approved by Order PCI/487/2019 by the National Security Council. Coordinated by the National Cybersecurity Council, this strategic document complements and develops the commitments in cybersecurity established in the 2017 National Security Strategy.

The Strategy's scope involves strengthening capabilities for detection, prevention, and response to cyber threats; ensuring the security and resilience of information and communication networks and systems across public administrations, critical infrastructures, the private sector and citizens; boosting the national cybersecurity industry and talent; and fostering international cooperation.

Although it is a key orientation document to deploy the national cybersecurity policies, the Strategy is a non-executive document, which means it is not legally binding. For this reason, its implementation depends on further legislative measures.

Implementation of the Strategy and supporting regulatory framework

The implementation of the National Cybersecurity Strategy is deployed through supplementary plans, the main one being the National Cybersecurity Plan (PNC). Approved in 2022 by the National Security Council, the PNC covers the period 2022–2025. As the main scheme to implement the national cybersecurity strategy, it serves as an executive guideline to translate strategic objectives into actionable actions, operationalizing the 2019 Strategy through over 150 impact initiatives and a budget over 1 billion euros.

The strategic actions of the Central Government in the field of cybersecurity are also complemented within the Strategic Plan against Cybercrime (2021).

Supporting Regulatory and Strategic Frameworks

Spain's cybersecurity governance is supported by a comprehensive set of regulatory and strategic instruments that complement and reinforce the National Cybersecurity Strategy and the National Cybersecurity Plan.

- **National Security Framework (ENS):** This framework regulates the security policy concerning the use of electronic means by public administrations and collaborating entities, for which compliance with the ENS is mandatory. First approved in 2010, Royal Decree 311/2022 significantly updated the framework, aligning it with current cybersecurity needs, expanding requirements such as continuous monitoring, supply chain protection, training, and defining clear roles for security management.
- **Critical Infrastructure Protection Law (Law 8/2011):** This law established measures for protecting critical infrastructures and created the National Centre for the Protection of Critical Infrastructure (CNPIC).
- **National Security Law (Law 36/2015):** This legislation provides the foundational framework for the governance of cybersecurity and supports the protection of critical infrastructures.
- **5G Regulation (Royal Decree-Law 7/2022):** It defines security requirements for the deployment and operation of 5G networks, covering supply chain management and risk mitigation. A later Royal Decree (April 2024) introduced the specific ENS applicable to 5G Networks.
- **European Transpositions:** The Spanish system was significantly influenced by the transposition of the original NIS Directive (2016) and now has started the process to transpose the NIS2 Directive (2022).

Recent developments and ongoing reforms

Currently, the strategic and legislative landscape in Spain is experimenting updates, driven by the increasing number of cyber incidents in recent years (up 16.6% in 2024 according to INCIBE), the increased sophistication of threats and the regulatory mandates from the EU.

Compliance with NIS2 directive requests a greater coordination among stakeholders and the establishment of stricter notification obligations to essential entities. At the same time, the increasing sophistication of cybersecurity threats, driven by the fast adoption of new technologies, especially artificial intelligence, has arisen the urgency of a more coordinated national response. Recent high-impact incidents, such as the cyberattack

suffered by the Spain's State Public Employment Service (SEPE) in 2021, have proven the need to adapt Spain's cybersecurity policy framework to this rapidly evolving threat environment.

To adapt to the new EU regulatory mandates and provide a better answer to the new risks, the main ongoing reforms are:

- **National Cybersecurity Strategy revision:** The 2019 Strategy is currently in the process of revision. The National Security Council approved the procedure for drafting a new strategy in April 2025.
- **NIS2 transposition:** Directive (EU) 2022/2555 (NIS2) mandates that member states to update their legal frameworks. Spain is transposing this directive through the Preliminary Draft of the Cybersecurity Coordination and Governance Law (approved in January 2025). This legislative project is expected to be urgently parliamentary processed in the upcoming months. It introduces enhanced obligations for essential entities (including stricter compliance and proactive supervision) and assigns direct responsibilities to their senior management.
- **National Cybersecurity Centre:** The draft NIS2 transposition law proposes a new governance structure, with the creation of the National Cybersecurity Centre as the single competent authority for cybersecurity. This new entity will act as a direction, promotion and coordination body.
- **Budgetary reinforcement:** In May 2025, the Central Government approved a 1,157 million euros investment plan aimed at strengthening cybersecurity, as part of the Industrial and Technological Security and Defence Plan. This budgetary dotation will complement the actions included in the National Cybersecurity Plan.

3.2 Main stakeholders in the country

Spain's cybersecurity ecosystem is articulated under a multi-stakeholder governance model, in which public organisations have a dominant coordination role, despite the significant economic and technological capacity of the private sector. This pluralistic

structure combines the state authority with network-based mechanisms for information sharing and collaborative action.

Key governmental stakeholders

The institutional landscape of cybersecurity governance in Spain is grounded in the National Security System, featuring a structure that is plural and atomized. The Presidency of the Government directs this framework, involving also the Ministry of Defence, Ministry of Interior and Ministry for digital transformation and public services, and supported by several coordinating and operational bodies.

Coordination and Political Direction Bodies

- National Security Council (CSN): The highest governmental body responsible for designing and coordinating comprehensive national-level security policies and strategies, including the National Cybersecurity Strategy, and supervise crisis management and response. The Council reports directly to the Government of Spain and is chaired by the President.
- Department of Homeland Security (DSN): A technical assistance body reporting to the Cabinet Office of the Presidency of the Government. The DSN is central to the coordination network, holding the vice-presidency and secretariat of the National Cybersecurity Council (CNC). It coordinates the ministries and public institutions at the national level.
- National Cybersecurity Council (CNC): A collegiate body that supports the CSN, with the main objective of strengthening coordination, collaboration, and cooperation among public administrations with cybersecurity competencies, and between public and private sectors. The CNC is responsible for guiding the development of national cybersecurity strategies.

Operational and Technical bodies

The national cybersecurity governance in the public sector deploys four leading operational bodies, hosted across three different Ministries (Defence, Interior, and Digital

Transformation and public services). These four organs are pivotal in managing incident response and cyber defence.

Organisation	Ministry/Department	Description
National Cryptologic Centre (CCN) & CCN-CERT	National Intelligence Centre (CNI), Ministry of Defence	It is an intelligence service that provides technical coordination among public administrations for response to cyberattacks. and disseminates best practices (CCN-STIC guides). Despite being an intelligence service, it adopts an accessible approach towards society, hosting the Platform for Notification and Monitoring of Cyber Incidents , a single point of contact to facilitate response coordination among national stakeholders. It also disseminates best practices through the CCN-STIC guides.
Spanish National Cybersecurity Institute (INCIBE) & INCIBE-CERT	Ministry for digital transformation and public service	It promotes cybersecurity for citizens, companies (with a special focus on SMEs), and strategic sectors. Operates the largest CERT in Spain, handling incidents from citizens, companies, and critical operators (via the 017 speed-dial number). It also promotes cybersecurity culture, awareness and skills. Acts as the National Coordination Centre of the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre.
Joint Cyberspace Command (MCCE)	Ministry of Defence	It is the military cyber defence organ, in charge of responding to cyber-attacks affecting military operations. It is responsible for the direction, control, and execution of actions to ensure a free and secure action of the national Armed Forces in cyberspace, as well as reinforcing national defence in this domain.
National Centre for the Protection of Critical Infrastructure (CNPIC)	Secretary of State for Security, Ministry of Interior	It is the organ responsible of the promotion, supervision and coordination of policies oriented to the protection of critical infrastructures in Spain.

Although this apparent fragmentation, the framework is designed to promote coordination and joint response to cybersecurity incidents. In this regard, the CNPIC hosts the Cybersecurity Coordination Office (OCC), which is the national operational coordination point for information exchange on cyberattacks. It acts as the CSIRT of the Ministry of Interior, coordinating with INCIBE-CERT, CCN-CERT and other national CSIRTs (such as those of critical operators, the National Police, and the Ministry of Defence). It also operates the Cybercrime Observatory of the Ministry of the Interior. In the same line, as stated before, the CCN-CERT manages the Platform for Notification and Monitoring of Cyber Incidents, a one-stop window to coordinate cyber incidents response and coordination among all public and private national stakeholders. When an organisation experiences a cyberattack or identifies a vulnerability in its security system, it can report the incident through the Platform, which updates the information in real time and notifies the other users. The MCCE has organised Cyber Bastions, cyber defence exercises to test national capacity in realistic environments. The objective is to train operative coordination between the armed forces and national entities to improve the readiness to provide a joint and rapid response to potential threats.

The legal framework also enhances cooperation among the different operating bodies and public administrations. For instance, the National Security Framework (ENS) mandates minimum security requirements for public administrations and collaborating entities, ensuring their alignment and a coordinated defence posture against cyber incidents.

Involvement of the private sector in Cybersecurity initiatives

The private sector is indispensable to the Spanish cybersecurity ecosystem, due to its high economic and technological capacity. The sector plays multiple roles, from essential service provision to driving technology transfer and filling the public sector's resource gaps.

Major cybersecurity and technological companies are the best equipped with respect to human resources, infrastructure, technology, and funding. They hold a greater concentration of expertise and are actively involved in the national cybersecurity ecosystem. They are the primary providers of cybersecurity services, benefiting from the high level of externalization in the cybersecurity field required by private companies in

other sectors. In fact, according to Deloitte's 2024 Cybersecurity in Spain survey (based on surveys to CISOs of Spanish companies), in 2022, 63% of Spanish companies outsourced their cybersecurity services, particularly for operations and maintenance tasks. Moreover, they are often at the forefront of research and development, developing new cybersecurity standards and protocols. Examples of these companies are GMV, SIRT, INDRA, TELEFÓNICA and AIRBUS.

SMEs represent 99.8% of the Spanish private sector. However, they are often described by experts as unaware about IT security measures, and lacking both the financial resources and the human capital required to tackle cyber threats effectively. Non-tech SMEs are the least equipped and the most vulnerable segment of the private sector. Technological SMEs implementing cybersecurity solutions in these non-tech SME's business environments play a relevant role in upgrading their readiness levels to tackle potential threats, and to increase their awareness and cybersecurity culture. However, most of the cybersecurity solutions offered by Spanish companies to the internal market are developed by third countries. This high dependence on external services makes the cybersecurity supply chain one of the most critical vulnerabilities of the country.

Critical Infrastructure Providers

As mentioned in previous sections, the protection of critical infrastructures, such as energy, finance, water, transport, health or ICT, is a foundational aspect of Spain's cybersecurity framework, governed by the Critical Infrastructure Protection Law 8/2011.

Collaboration between public institutions, mainly the CNPIC, and critical infrastructure operators is compulsory by law, promoting an increase in trust between these actors. The ongoing transposition of the NIS2 and DORA regulations mandates new requirements on operators of essential services and the financial sector, increasing their compliance obligations.

Professional Associations

Non-profit industry and professional associations play a crucial role in providing collective input on policies, fostering R&D and open innovation initiatives and enhancing the

cohesion within the national cybersecurity ecosystem, particularly concerning the vast landscape of SMEs in Spain. Some of the most relevant are:

- **AMETIC (Multisectoral Association of Electronics, Information and Communication Technologies):** The representative association of the digital industry in Spain. With over 50 years of experience in the sector, it represents the industry's view to influence public policies. AMETIC has dedicated working commissions on cybersecurity and on dual-use technologies.
- **ISMS Forum Spain:** An organisation founded in 2007 to promote the development, knowledge, and culture of Information Security in Spain, with regional (Andalucía, Barcelona, Basque Country, Galicia and Valencia) and international (México and Portugal) chapters.
- **CyberLur:** The Spanish Cybersecurity Innovation Cluster. Gathers companies, research centres, and public bodies to promote collaborative innovation.
- **Women4Cyber (W4C) Spain:** Works to increase female talent in cybersecurity, where women represent only 31% of the sector's labour force. It also supports female entrepreneurship in cybersecurity through programs like the W4C Startup School.

Academic and research institutions contributing to cybersecurity

Academic and research institutions are central actors in the ecosystem, as they develop national capabilities, generate knowledge, and foster the talent needed for the long-run sustainability of Spain's Cybersecurity Strategy and resilience. Research and innovation are critical to anticipate and face cyber threats, as well as to implement disruptive technologies to enhance cyber defence capabilities. Spain actively participates in European R&D programs like Horizon Europe, where it has achieved substantial returns. The main research and innovation drivers at the national level are:

- **Spanish National Research Council (CSIC):** Spain's largest public research organisation, actively involved in cutting-edge areas like cryptography, AI, quantum communication, or cybersecurity. The CSIC works to transfer its innovations through technology transfer offices (TTOs).

- **Centre for Technological Development and Innovation (CDTI):** A Public Corporate Entity under the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities. It provides financial support for R&D projects, some of which with dual-use orientation, in a wide variety of technological fields like cybersecurity, promoting collaboration between public research and technological centers and the private sector. Examples of ongoing CDTI programs explicitly including cybersecurity as a strategic area are the Misiones, Cervera and Neotec programs.
- **Universities:** Key actors in the ecosystem, running cybersecurity research centres and participating in R&D programs and partnerships, as well as generating the new talent in the field.
- **Technological centres:** These organisations focus on technology transfer, developing mature technologies (with high TRLs) for a later transfer and exploitation in the market by the industry. They participate in financing programs like the Cervera program (CDTI) or Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) initiatives (lead by INCIBE in the cybersecurity area). Spain has an important network of top-level regional technology centres, such as Eurecat and i2Cat in Catalonia, Tecnalia and Vicomtech in the Basque Country, InnovalRV in Andalucia or Gradiant in Galicia.
- **Spanish Network of Excellence on Cybersecurity Research (RENIC):** A network dedicated to fostering collaboration between universities, technological centres, and the market to better align research with real-world societal needs.

Public-Private Partnerships and collaborative frameworks

Collaboration and trust are fundamental to reinforce the resilience of the Spanish and the European cybersecurity ecosystem, especially because a single cyberattack can have widespread national and international effects, raising the need for a common framework of cooperation.

Spain has implemented several formalized structures intended to bridge the public and private sectors, improving resource exchange and coordination:

- **National Cybersecurity Forum (FNC):** Identified as a superstructural node, it is coordinated by the DSN (Chair/Secretariat), together with INCIBE (First Vice-Chair)

and CCN (Second Vice-Chair). Its mission is to group and coordinate societal participation in cybersecurity, explicitly promoting public-private collaboration. Its objectives include to improve cooperation between the public and private sectors in enhancing cyber industry and R&D, the promotion of specialized cybersecurity training, and the systematization of regulatory cooperation. Despite its main role at promoting public-private collaboration in cybersecurity, the FNC is currently altruistic, and lacks dedicated financial resources for a broader action, being it its main limitation.

- **National SOC Network (RNS):** It constitutes an internal collaborative network driven by the CCN-CERT, integrating public and private Security Operations Centres (SOCs) to facilitate a rapid threat intelligence sharing. To be part of the network, organisations must agree to share information. This coordination allows faster responses to cyberattacks and an improvement of collective maturity and readiness.
- **Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI):** To stimulate national R&D, INCIBE and CDTI have launched Public Procurement of Innovation initiatives, aimed to fund high TRL cybersecurity technologies that can meet actual demand-side needs, ensuring their transfer to the market. This kind of programs often imply the establishment of collaborative consortiums, which improves the ecosystem cohesion. The main Public Procurement of Innovation initiative is promoted by INCIBE, with a 224 million euros budget.
- **Defence collaboration programs:** The main defence collaboration initiative is the COINCIDENTE Program. Managed by the Ministry of Defence's General Directorate of Defence Industry Strategy and Innovation, this program promotes the integration of civilian technologies developed by private companies and research and technological centres into defence capabilities and supports dual-use R&D projects.

Besides these formal collaboration mechanisms, it is important to highlight that collaboration among national cybersecurity stakeholders also occurs through non-formal channels, through professional forums and conferences like ENISE and CyberCamp (both organised by INCIBE). National stakeholders also have created informal and trusted peer networks, such as private groups of CISOs, to share best practices and foster the community.

Despite these structures, collaboration among the national cybersecurity agents faces severe challenges, due to systemic issues related to trust among the public and private agents, and the fragmented and over-bureaucratic landscape.

3.3 National cybersecurity challenges and gaps

As previously mentioned, Spain is ranked highly internationally for its legislative framework and institutional commitment to cybersecurity, classifying as a tier-1 country in the 2024 edition of the Global Cybersecurity Index, and as the fourth best country globally and the third in Europe in the 2021 edition. However, the country faces critical challenges that compromise the effectiveness of its security strategies and policies, and its ability to achieve a comprehensive cyber resilience. The implementation of the National Cybersecurity Strategy is considered moderately effective due to several structural gaps.

Fragmentation and uneven governance implementation

A fundamental challenge in Spain's cybersecurity framework is the fragmentation of competencies and resources across national, regional, and sectoral levels, leading to a plural and somewhat atomized ecosystem. In fact, the decentralized nature of Spain's political organisation results in a heterogeneous implementation of cybersecurity policies. Local and regional Public Administrations are particularly affected, often lacking specialized personnel and the required maturity to uniformly apply existing national regulations, such as the National Security Framework (ENS). This situation creates uncertainty and difficult multi-level coordination.

Furthermore, the absence of a clear and single national cybersecurity reference point aggravates the situation, generating confusion to all the ecosystem agents that seek public administrations guidance, especially SMEs. In fact, according to Deloitte's 2024 Cybersecurity in Spain survey, a 53% of them identify regulatory compliance as a challenge for their organisation, making it the fourth most frequently cited hurdle.

This institutional fragmentation means that the overall defensive readiness to face cyberattacks is only as strong as its weakest node. Local Public Administrations become

the most vulnerable node in the chain of national cyber defence. Recent cyberattacks affecting local Public Administrations in cities like Melilla, Seville, or the Provincial Council of Jaén highlight this vulnerability, which often leads to the temporary paralysis of public services. These incidents demonstrate the failure to implement the required cybersecurity standards uniformly at the local level.

To address it, Spain is currently in the transposition process of the NIS2 Directive. IN January 2025 the Government approved the Preliminary Draft of the Cybersecurity Coordination and Governance Law, which seeks to implement NIS2 and proposes to simplify national-level cybersecurity governance by creating a National Cybersecurity Centre as the sole competent authority, acting as a direction, promotion and coordination organ.

Skill shortages and resource constraints

Spain faces a severe and persistent challenge regarding human capital scarcity and the capacity to attract and retain specialized cybersecurity talent.

According to INCIBE, the deficit of qualified cybersecurity professionals reached 26,000 workers in 2022 (the most recent year available), and the challenge has intensified significantly in the following years, with an estimated deficit of around 40,000 workers in 2024. Moreover, the NIS2 Directive transposition is expected to intensify the demand for thousands of new CISOs and specialized teams, boosting the demand for cybersecurity profiles and enlarging the gap even more.

This lack of specialized talent translates directly into a high dependency on external resources, for both private and public stakeholders. Notably, 68% of the business organisations report that they outsource more than half of their cybersecurity staff.

On the formal education side, Spain currently offers more than 100 university-level cybersecurity programs (bachelor's degrees, masters and specializations), alongside more than 120 educational centres offering vocational training programs. Nevertheless, the increasing gap between the supply of cybersecurity professionals and a fast-growing demand makes the current supply of formal training courses insufficient to meet the labour market needs.

To tackle the gap, the Government has reinforced investment, exemplified by the over 1,000 million euros investment via the National Cybersecurity Plan in the period 2022–2025, and the 1,157 million euros investment plan approved in May 2025 for strengthening cybersecurity. These plans include cybersecurity education and skills development as one of the main priorities. In parallel, public organisms such as INCIBE and the CCN actively manage programs like CyberCamp and ATENEA to foster cybersecurity culture and generate and attract talent in the field.

Ecosystem vulnerabilities: SMEs and supply chain risk

Most of the Spanish business landscape is composed by SMEs, representing 99.8% of the total business sector. SMEs are highly vulnerable, because they are often unaware of IT security measures and are the worst equipped label of the value chain, due to human capital and resource limitations. This structural weakness is deepened by the high dependence on third-party suppliers, posing a high supply chain risk. In fact, according to the above-mentioned Deloitte's report, Spanish organisations outsource most of their cybersecurity tasks, spending 66% of their cybersecurity budgets on outsourced services. However, most companies lack comprehensive control mechanisms over their service providers.

This concern is reflected in the fact that 68% of CISOs identify the management of cybersecurity across the supply chain (third parties) as one of the main challenges they face, being the third most frequently cited after threat sophistication and ensuring business operations and continuity.

The low cyber maturity of SMEs creates a massive attack surface area for cybercriminals, with supply chain weaknesses serving as a primary vector for high-impact incidents. The massive ransomware attack suffered by the Spanish State Public Employment Service (SEPE) in March 2021 demonstrated the dependency on external capabilities, forcing the Ministry of Labour to urgently award contracts to external companies for incident remediation. In order to address these gaps, INCIBE offers specific programs (like *INCIBE Emprende*) to support start-ups and improve SME capabilities. There is also an ongoing effort to implement dynamic segmentation models to enhance the control of critical suppliers, many organisations still manage third-party risk without specialized tools.

Barriers to collaboration and lack of trust

Collaboration between public and private sectors, essential for effective information sharing and collective intelligence, is severely hindered by cultural barriers and a fundamental lack of trust.

Distrust is one of the most frequently mentioned barriers to share sensitive information. Private entities are reluctant to report incidents or vulnerabilities, due to the fear of reputational damage or economic loss, particularly when incidents could expose potential non-compliance mistakes. This situation is aggravated by perceived conflicts of interest within the national cybersecurity ecosystem. Experts point out that public organisations are sometimes linked to competing private cybersecurity companies due to the outsource of some operations and services derived from resource constraints, leading competitors to refuse sharing critical intelligence. These low levels of information sharing prevent the development of robust collective cyber intelligence, making it difficult to generate preventative alerts based on shared threat patterns.

To build trust and foster collaboration, there are several mechanisms. For instance, the National Cybersecurity Forum acts as a superstructural node designed to promote public-private collaboration and cohesion. Other mechanisms like the National SOC Network require companies to share information to participate, incentivizing collaboration. Furthermore, mandatory notification obligations derived from the NIS2 transposition also aim to increase the flow of information, although a high sanction risk could discourage reporting.

3.4 International cooperation and partnerships in cybersecurity

International cooperation constitutes an essential pillar of Spain's cybersecurity strategy, as cyber threats transcend national borders and require a coordinated global response. Spain's engagement is primarily focused on multilateral organisations, particularly those within the European and Atlantic spheres, aiming to enhance national resilience, technological capacity, and global influence.

Participation in international initiatives and organisations

EU Framework

The future of Spain's cybersecurity governance and policies is fundamentally linked to regulatory developments of the EU. The objective of EU policy in the cybersecurity area is to ensure a global, open, and secure internet. Spain is adhered to the EU regulatory instruments designed to standardize security models across Europe, such as the NIS Directives (NIS and NIS2, currently in the transposition phase) and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Moreover, Spain is actively involved with the major European cybersecurity bodies and networks:

- **ENISA (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity):** Spain participates in networks and projects coordinated by ENISA.
- **ECCC (European Cybersecurity Competence Centre) Network:** As previously mentioned, the Spanish National Cybersecurity Institute (INCIBE) is the National Coordination Centre (NCC) of the ECCC, facilitating the national connection with the European network of coordination centres.
- **European Union CSIRTs Network:** Spanish Public Administrations participate in the network of Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs) across Europe.

In addition, Spain is highly engaged in cybersecurity R&D collaborative projects at the European level. The country capitalizes significantly on funds from European framework programs like Horizon Europe, where it has strong participation in Cluster 3, which addresses security-related innovative projects, and the Digital Europe Programme.

NATO and Defence Cooperation

Spain is deeply integrated into the cybersecurity defence structures of the North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO). For example, Spanish Armed Forces participate in joint cyber-defence structures by the NATO; and the Joint Cyberspace Command (MCCE) participates in NATO's defence structure. In parallel, Spain is a founding country and member of the steering committee of the NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (CCD COE) in Tallinn, which aims to enhance the Alliance cyber defence capabilities through research, training and cooperation.

Spain also supports initiatives aimed at developing technologies for military application, such as the promotion of dual-use technologies through NATO's Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic (DIANA), launched in 2022. INCIBE has been designated as an accelerator for cybersecurity startups within the DIANA program.

Spain utilizes NATO's formal multinational exercises for cooperation and intelligence exchange, being the most relevant the Cyber Coalition, NATO's annual flagship cyber defence exercise (involving the MCCE as the national representative), as well as the Locked Shields, a multinational training exercise for CSIRTs organized by the NATO CCD COE.

Other international cooperation mechanisms

Spain complements international cybersecurity cooperation through international forums, conventions, and targeted bilateral agreements to enhance policy development and technical capacity.

Good examples of this are the Spain's Memorandum on Cybersecurity Cooperation with Argentina, signed in 2023, and the bilateral Cyber and Digital Dialogue with the USA, with regular meetings and joint declarations, such as the one issued in June of 2024.

Spain is also strongly committed in international cooperation against cybercrime. The country ratified the **Budapest Convention on Cybercrime** in 2010, the primary international treaty to combat cybercrime and facilitate international cooperation in this area. In 2022, Spain also signed the Second Additional Protocol to this Convention.

Impact on the National Cybersecurity Framework

International collaborations yield direct and positive effects on the national cybersecurity framework, through different angles:

- **Improved operational capabilities:** Participation in multinational exercises allows Spanish organisations (military, CERTs and security forces) to test procedures, technologies, and coordination mechanisms in realistic scenarios, providing the expertise to strengthen technical interoperability and the speed of response to real incidents.

- **Policy and Strategy Alignment:** Integration into EU and NATO frameworks mandates that Spain align its national strategies and regulations to meet common cybersecurity standards, ensuring that national policies are connected with broader European and NATO strategic objectives.
- **R&D and Industrial Growth:** EU-funded programs enable Spain to develop its own cybersecurity technologies and solutions, enhancing the national industrial value chain. These programs, often involving dual-use technologies, benefit both the civil and military sectors, improving the positioning and competitiveness of the Spanish defence industry.
- **International Positioning:** Spain aims to position itself as an international cybersecurity hub. Its solid engagement in EU and NATO's frameworks enhance its diplomatic influence in global cybersecurity policy design.

Challenges and Limitations in International Cooperation Efforts

Despite successful cooperation experiences, Spain faces several limitations that affect the effectiveness and sustainability of its international partnerships:

- **Talent and Resource Gap:** Spain experiences a shortage of specialized cybersecurity personnel in both the public and private sectors. This limits the capacity to operate effectively, adopt new technologies, and participate in multiple complex international projects.
- **Strategic Autonomy and External Dependence:** Spain, like other EU members, must mitigate the dependence on external technologies, platforms, and suppliers that might trigger vulnerabilities. The lack of a robust national industry in the cybersecurity field often means R&D focuses on European priorities rather than purely national needs.
- **Regulatory and Bureaucratic Hurdles:** Harmonizing laws, standards, and procedures across countries is complex, involving both legal and interoperability barriers. Furthermore, experts note that excessive bureaucracy can slow down the implementation of EU cybersecurity regulations in Spain.
- **Disparities in Public Sector Capabilities:** Differences in the maturity and resources of regional and local administrations mean not all entities can effectively comply with the

cybersecurity standards demanded by international agreements, potentially creating bottlenecks in compliance and response.

4. Technology transfer framework

In the current context of fast evolving threats, effective technology transfer is crucial to foster the cybersecurity resilience of Spain and enhancing national sovereignty.

This section explores the mechanisms through which cybersecurity technologies are transferred to the market within and between different sectors, including civilian and defence industries. It assesses existing technology transfer policies, identifies best practices, and highlights challenges faced in facilitating a smooth transfer of cybersecurity solutions.

4.1. Definition and importance of technology transfer in cybersecurity

Technology transfer refers to the process by which knowledge, technologies, and innovative solutions originating from research and other non-market environments, such as academia, national defence organisations or technological centres, once they are mature enough, are deployed to the market to reach potential end-users.

In the specific area of cybersecurity, technology transfer is characterized by the need for a rapid transition of new technologies and solutions from research to market due to the fast pace of threat evolution. Successful technology transfer is crucial to ensure the scalability and sustainability of cybersecurity technological solutions, placing them in operational settings to enhance the national capacities in front of the increasing cyberthreats.

Moreover, technology transfer plays a key strategic role in reducing Spain's dependence on non-European cybersecurity technologies, such as those from Israel and the United States, which are among the main external providers in the field. Without national and European property cybersecurity technologies, national resilience can be compromised.

The successful transfer to the market of national cybersecurity technologies strengthens the capacity of Spain to prevent, respond and recover from cyberattacks.

At the same time, technology transfer maximizes the social returns of public R&D investment and contributes not only to national cyber resilience but also to foster the European strategic autonomy in this critical sector. This occurs both through the final product itself and through the synergies created with other EU-level research and innovation projects and initiatives.

Technology transfer also serves as a catalyst to stimulate the dual-use dimension of technologies, enabling the adoption civil-oriented innovation to defence-context applications, and vice versa. In the case of cybersecurity, where most technologies are inherently dual-use, this integration between both spheres supports public-private collaboration and grants access to cutting-edge knowledge and capabilities to both the civil and the defence sectors. Synergies among these sectors are fundamental to ensure the cyber resilience of Spain, directly contributing to the national and European strategic autonomy.

4.2. Legal and regulatory framework governing technology transfer

Spain's legal and regulatory framework governing technology transfer is complex, integrating national regulation with comprehensive European mandates. In the specific case of cybersecurity, the framework is mainly compliance-driven, creating demand-side regulatory drivers for secure technologies. However, it also imposes bureaucratic barriers that prevent an agile transition from research to market.

National legal framework for technology transfer

The national framework for technology transfer lies in an exhaustive regulatory foundation that integrates science, innovation and security legislation. The Spanish Strategy for Science, Technology and Innovation (EECTI) 2021-2027 is a pivotal document in this regard, aligned with the Digital Spain 2026 agenda.

One of the EECTI's main objectives is to foster two-way collaboration between science and industry, supporting specific measures such as Action Line 11, which aims to promote effective mechanisms for knowledge transfer, cooperation and exchange between the public and private spheres.

While the EECTI sets broad goals and priorities at the country level, the key legislative document to implement technology transfer policies in Spain is the Law on Science, Technology and Innovation (Law 14/2011), which was amended in 2022 through the Law 17/2022.

As part of the implementation of the EECTI, one of the main objectives of this 2022 reform is to boost technology and knowledge transfer between public research and the whole society, recognizing technology transfer as a right, duty and merit within the Spanish R&D system.

Regulatory drivers for cybersecurity technology transfer

Regarding the specific case of cybersecurity, the EECTI includes cybersecurity as a national strategic line under the thematic group "Security for Society", which replicates the structure of the Cluster 3 of the Horizon Europe Funding Program (2021-2027).

In fact, the EECTI prioritizes R&D efforts towards specific cutting-edge cybersecurity areas, such as quantum communications and cryptography, post quantum encryption, secure software engineering, cybersecurity applications in industrial environments and critical infrastructures and systems for the detection, prediction and attribution against cyber-attacks.

Besides the general Spanish science and innovation framework, specific compliance regulatory requirements establish demand-driven incentives that promote the development and market adoption of secure and certified cybersecurity solutions.

Among them, the most prominent is the National Security Framework (2022), which sets minimum security requirements and mandatory compliance mechanisms for public administrations and collaborating entities, and ensures both the system protection and solution certification.

The National Cryptologic Centre (CCN-CERT) acts as the implementation body. It manages a catalogue of certified products and technological developments (STIC product catalogue), that incentivizes research entities and private companies to develop and transfer to the public sector technologies that comply with national security certification standards.

Additional relevant legislation includes the Critical Infrastructure Protection Law (2011), which sets cybersecurity and protection obligations for operators of essential services and critical sectors, driving the demand for advanced cybersecurity solutions. Moreover, the Royal Decree-Law 7/2022 on the security of 5G electronic communications, networks and services, encourages the development and adoption of domestic technological solutions to diversify suppliers and reduce external dependencies in the 5G domain.

In addition, cybersecurity technologies, for their inherent dual-use nature, usually fall under dual-use control regulations, which will be explored in Chapter 6.

To sum up, the principal mean by which national regulation facilitates cybersecurity technology transfer is through the establishment of cybersecurity compliance requirements, creating a market demand for certified technological solutions and incentivizing technological transfer.

European and international frameworks

As a member of the European Union, Spain operates under the European Research Area (ERA), and is committed to EU principles on open science, data governance and intellectual property.

It is an active participant in EU-level initiatives such as Horizon Europe, the Digital Europe Program, the European Defence Fund (EDF), and the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC), which ensures the alignment with the European innovation and technology transfer framework.

Spain also participates in international cooperation networks in innovation such as EUREKA or NATO's Science and Technology Organisation (STO), supporting transnational innovation and transfer of cybersecurity technologies.

Main challenges and barriers

Despite Spain's comprehensive regulatory framework, technology transfer in the cybersecurity domain still faces several structural and operational bottlenecks that prevent a smoother deployment and commercialization of innovative solutions:

- **Bureaucratic and Administrative Rigidity:** Excessive bureaucracy and slow administrative procedures, particularly in cross-border technology transfer and the commercial exploitation of publicly funded R&D results, limit both the agility and capacity to deploy R&D results into commercial applications. For example, public procurement processes often require detailed technical specifications for technologies that are still under development.
- **Intellectual Property Rights Complexity:** The protective approach to Intellectual Property Rights in public research entities, such as universities, can unintentionally hinder technology transfer. A better clarification of these rights in multi-stakeholder collaborative projects would facilitate the deployment of cybersecurity technologies to the market.
- **Certification Barriers:** Strict national certification standards, while promoting security, can sometimes act as a barrier to the adoption of cutting-edge internationally compliant technologies that have not yet completed the national approval process, discouraging cross-border technology transfer.

4.3. National institutions responsible for facilitating technology transfer

Spain's institutional setting to foster cybersecurity technology transfer is vast, integrating in an interconnected setting public administration (including defence and intelligence bodies), research organisations, technological centres, and the private sector. These actors are the operational bodies where the national science, technology and innovation system lies on. Cohesion among these stakeholders at the national level is enforced through the Interministerial Committee for Science, Technology and Innovation, and the National Cybersecurity Council for the specific domain of cybersecurity.

Government agencies and defence bodies

Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities

The Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities lead the design and implementation of national technology transfer policies under the Law 2011. Through the State Research Agency (AEI) and, especially, the Centre for Industrial Technological Development (CDTI), it funds and coordinates R&D initiatives in the cybersecurity domain.

Centre for industrial technological development (CDTI)

CDTI is a public entity which main objective is to strengthen the competitiveness of Spanish industry by facilitating the transfer of technology and knowledge from research institutions to the business sector, being the main operational body through which the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities deploy technology transfer policies.

As the reference public entity that fosters technology transfer, CDTI supports business-led innovation through own funding instruments such as *Misiones*, *Cervera*, and *Neotec*, playing a strategic role in promoting public-private collaboration to bridge the research and the industrial application domains. In particular, the 2025 edition of these funding programmes has a clear dual-use security technologies' orientation (including cybersecurity), with dedicated tracks on the topic.

Misiones Ciencia e Innovación is a program that supports cooperative R&D projects led by the private sector, addressing specific “missions” in national strategic technological areas. The 2025 call incorporates a mission on “capabilities for strategic autonomy in security and defence”, which targets cybersecurity technologies.

Cervera is a program that supports networks of technological centres, through an accreditation as centres of excellence, to develop strategic R&D initiatives in strategic technological domains. The 2025 call allocates 50 million euros to foster dual-use technologies, including, among others, cybersecurity.

Neotec is a program that supports early-stage technology-based start-ups to transform research-derived technologies into commercial companies. The 2025 call includes a dedicated funding reserve of 150 million euros for dual-use technologies, aligned with Spain’s Technology and Innovation Strategy for Defence (2025) led by the Ministry of Defence.

CDTI also promotes the access of the national innovation stakeholders to international innovation programs, such as Horizon Europe (where Cluster 3 “Civil Security for Society” targets cybersecurity), Eureka and the European Space Agency (ESA) ones. CDTI acts as the national contact point for these international innovation programs.

National cybersecurity institute (INCIBE)

In addition to its central responsibility in the management of cybersecurity incidents and developing cybersecurity awareness in Spain, the National Cybersecurity Institute (INCIBE), under the Ministry for Digital Transformation and the Civil Service, is a key catalyst in promoting cybersecurity innovation and technology transfer.

The Public Procurement of Innovation Programme is the main INCIBE’s instrument to promote cybersecurity technology transfer. It was launched in 2021 with a total budget of around 224 million euros.

As a cutting-edge tech policy instrument, it functions as a demand-side innovation driver, identifying unmet cybersecurity challenges in public administration and society, and commissioning R&D services from research and technological centres and private innovative companies to generate high Technology Readiness Level (TRL) technological solutions to solve them. The resulting solutions are integrated into public infrastructures, guaranteeing a successful market deployment of the developed technologies.

INCIBE's Public Procurement of Innovation program is framed through four action lines: R&D programs with the cybersecurity industry, Technological solutions for cybersecurity in SMEs, Technological solutions for cybersecurity in strategic sectors, and Technological solutions to public sector challenges. Until now, it has generated innovations in diverse cybersecurity areas, such as critical infrastructure protection, 5G security, cloud trust services and threat intelligence, boosting the national cybersecurity technological capacity.

Additionally, INCIBE supports entrepreneurship and innovation through programs such as INCIBE Emprende, to foster the incubation and acceleration of cybersecurity start-ups, and Cybersecurity Ventures, to mentor early-stage cybersecurity start-ups and connect them with investors, helping innovative cybersecurity companies to scale-up their businesses.

Other key government actors

The CCN, under the National Intelligence Centre (CNI), through the STIC Certification Framework and its catalogue of certified products, certifies and promotes security technologies developed by Spanish companies, including cybersecurity solutions. Through this mechanism, the CCN acts as a technology transfer facilitator.

At the same time, the Joint Cyberspace Command, under the Ministry of Defence, is a key actor in the adaptation of general and civilian technologies to specific defence needs and participates in specific R&D projects.

Also, under the Ministry of Defence, the General Directorate of Armament and Material (DGAM) manages the Program COINCIDENTE, designed to leverage civilian technologies for defence applications by selecting R&D demonstrators with defence functionality. The program promotes collaboration between industry, research centres and the army, reinforcing the dual-use technology transfer in Spain, including cybersecurity innovative solutions.

Research and innovation ecosystem

Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)

The CSIC leads cybersecurity research in areas like cryptography, secure communications and data protection. It holds a dedicated Vice-Presidency for knowledge Transfer, which promotes and manages the patenting, licensing and commercialisation of cybersecurity technologies developed by its research institutes.

Beyond the promotion of internal technology transfer, CSIC is highly engaged in national and European-level cybersecurity innovation consortiums and projects, including Cluster 3 of Horizon Europe and the European Cybersecurity Competence Network.

Universities and technological centres

Several Spanish universities, such as the Polytechnic University of Madrid, Polytechnic University of Catalonia or the University of Malaga host specialized cybersecurity research centres. Their Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) facilitate both the patenting and licensing, as well as the creation of spin-offs, fostering collaboration with industry.

Technological Centres act as industrial R&D hubs that enable to test and scale cybersecurity solutions, accelerating both innovation and the market readiness of new cybersecurity technologies. In this line, another key actor of the national cybersecurity technology transfer ecosystem is the National Network of Excellence in Cybersecurity Research (RENIC), which connects the academic and industrial stakeholders to boost the development and dissemination of new cybersecurity innovations among them.

Collaborative platforms, clusters and industry associations

National Cybersecurity Forum

The National Cybersecurity Forum, as a strategic platform to promote public-private collaboration in the cybersecurity field, facilitates the identification of national cybersecurity technological challenges and promotes collaborative approaches to develop solutions to overcome them. By acting as a hub for public-private cooperation in the cybersecurity field, the Forum plays a key role in enhancing technology transfer, ensuring that the new developments meet national cybersecurity needs.

Clusters and associations

Innovation clusters and associations, such as CyberLur, foster and coordinate the participation of SMEs and start-ups in collaborative R&D projects, granting them access to European and national cybersecurity funding programs and acting as bridges between research and industrial stakeholders. At the same time, Women4Cyber Spain launches acceleration programs like the Startup-School to promote female entrepreneurship in cybersecurity, contributing to the technology transfer in the field.

4.4. Incentives and barriers to technology transfer

Spain benefits from extensive national and European-level innovation public funding instruments and collaborative platforms, which reinforce the innovation in the cybersecurity sphere. Technology transfer is essential to transform the outcomes of this research into market solutions that enhance the country's resilience and industrial competitiveness. However, Spain still faces several structural and operational challenges that hamper cybersecurity technology transfer. This section outlines the main incentives and barriers for effective technology transfer in Spain, and their overall impact on the national cybersecurity ecosystem.

Main incentives for cybersecurity technology transfer

In recent years, participation in technology transfer activities is becoming increasingly attractive for the national cybersecurity stakeholders.

Public funding and acceleration programs

Financial incentives are central to drive cybersecurity technology transfer, as they mitigate the inherent risks of R&D in a fast-evolving domain that may prevent an organisation to develop new cybersecurity technologies. In this context, national and European-level funding schemes play a key role. Instruments such as the CDTI programs offer financial support for the organisations that develop high-TRL cybersecurity technologies, reducing the financial risks of R&D initiatives in the field.

Spain's public innovation policy has recently adopted demand-side mechanisms to accelerate the deployment of cybersecurity technologies to the market, being INCIBE Public Procurement of Innovation Program, launched in 2021, one of the most relevant initiatives in this regard, for both its budget allocation (around 224 million euros) and its impact in the national cybersecurity ecosystem.

Acceleration programs targeting cybersecurity startups, such as INCIBE Emprande and the Startup-School of Women4Cyber Spain, are also relevant mechanisms to incentivize the engagement of national cybersecurity agents in technology transfer initiatives.

Public-private partnerships and institutional reputation

The opportunity to engage in multistakeholder partnerships, involving both public and private entities, along with the institutional recognition gained through the participation in cutting-edge innovation projects, is another driver of cybersecurity technological transfer.

Engaging in technology transfer reinforces the strategic positioning of organisations within the national innovation and cybersecurity ecosystem, gaining visibility and public recognition, which opens the door for future collaboration opportunities with government agencies, critical infrastructure operators and major industry players.

Moreover, recent legal reforms, such as the 2022 amendment of the Law on Science, Technology and Innovation, acknowledge technological transfer as a professional merit and an institutional duty for public research organisations, incentivizing both institutions and researchers to actively participate in it.

Strategic autonomy and industrial competitiveness

Cybersecurity technology transfer is aligned with the broader national objectives of strategic autonomy and industrial competitiveness. In fact, it is a key mechanism to improve the innovation capacity of national stakeholders in the cybersecurity domain, making them more competitive in both the national and international markets.

Consequently, this enhanced industrial capacity reduces the dependencies from third countries in cybersecurity solutions, improving the resilience of the Spanish ecosystem. Technology transfer also contributes to talent development, helping to address talent shortages and build a more robust national innovation ecosystem. For these reasons, national stakeholders have incentives to foster it.

Main barriers for cybersecurity technology transfer

Despite these incentives, several structural and operation barriers limit the effective technology transfer to the market in the national cybersecurity ecosystem.

Cultural and trust barriers

Divergent objectives between public and private actors, where public institutions prioritize national security and regulatory compliance, and private organisations prioritize their profits, weaken collaboration in cybersecurity technology joint innovation and technology transfer initiatives.

Furthermore, the persistent lack of trust between public and private actors constrains the exchange of sensitive data and information that could accelerate cybersecurity technological development. In consequence, promising innovations often remain siloed within institutions instead of being transferred to the market.

In addition, within the national cybersecurity ecosystem, many organisations tend to prefer established foreign technologies, from countries like Israel or USA, over domestic solutions. This preference reduces market demand for Spanish cybersecurity technologies, undermining the national cybersecurity industrial base.

Regulatory and bureaucratic constraints

Complex administrative procedures hinder the efficient transfer of research outcomes to the market.

The national innovation ecosystem often prevents SMEs from participating in R&D funded programs, due to the long bureaucratic approval processes, delayed payments and restrictions in the eligibility criteriums, which impose excessive burdens that disincentivise their participation in the publicly funded programs.

In parallel, unclear rules regarding intellectual property ownership, in particular for projects co-developed with public institutions, can create disputes over licensing or revenue sharing. These uncertainties delay both the deployment of new technologies in the market and discourage private investors from supporting technology transfer initiatives.

In the specific case of cybersecurity, the inherent dual-use nature implies additional compliance burdens such as export control regulations, which restrict the internationalization of new cybersecurity solutions and further limits the engagement of private companies in innovation and technological transfer initiatives.

Resource and technical limitations

Limited financial and technical capacity within the ecosystem, especially among SMEs, constrains the deployment of advanced cybersecurity technologies to the market. Many organisations lack the resources to bridge the gap between the high TRLs achieved in research projects and the full-scale implementation required for a successful transfer of these technologies to the market.

The shortage of specialized talent further limits the operational capacity of both private companies and public institutions to manage technology transfer processes in an effective manner.

Impact on national cybersecurity resilience

The effectiveness of technology transfer in the Spanish cybersecurity ecosystem is determined by the interplay between incentives and structural barriers. While public national and EU investment programs, combined with regulatory-driven demand, have fostered cybersecurity technology transfer, directly contributing to the strategic autonomy of Spain, several persistent barriers limit the efficiency and reach of the system.

The result is a fragmented ecosystem that produces isolated success cases, rather than a cohesive innovation network capable of rapidly responding to emerging cyber threats.

To accelerate technology transfer and maximize its impact on the national cybersecurity ecosystem, Spain should simplify administrative procedures to reduce delays and incentivize SME participation, clarify intellectual property rules in multi-stakeholder projects to increase legal certainty and private investors confidence, foster a trust-based collaboration environment across the public and the private sectors to promote information sharing and joint innovation projects, and invest in talent development, to ensure the necessary capacities to bring high-TRL cybersecurity technologies to the market.

These types of policies, oriented towards the mitigation of the previously identified bottlenecks, would accelerate the transition of new technologies from research settings to commercial deployment, fostering Spain's cybersecurity resilience and contributing to the European strategic autonomy and digital sovereignty.

4.5. Examples of successful technology transfer initiatives

After analysing the main regulations, stakeholders, and programs promoting cybersecurity technology transfer in Spain, as well as the principal incentives and barriers, this section highlights specific examples of successful initiatives. These cases show how research and innovation outputs in cybersecurity are effectively transferred into operational environments, supporting both national security and industrial competitiveness.

CiberTRS

- **Description:** Spin-off from the Polytechnic University of Valencia (UPV) to transfer cyber-intelligence tools to the market. The technological development that enabled the creation of new solutions has been supported by the cybersecurity calls within the Cluster 3 of Horizon Europe.
- **Impacts:** Deploys advanced cyber-intelligence and monitoring systems to critical-infrastructure operators, increasing protection in key sectors.

CSIC-BACSI Collaboration

- **Description:** R&D collaboration between the CSIC and the Spanish Air and Space Force on the BACSI (“Connected, Sustainable, Intelligent Air Base”) project.
- **Impacts:** Advances research in intelligent, connected, and sustainable military base technologies, supporting the integration of R&D into operational defence settings.

SPARTA project

- **Description:** The project aims to promote the cybersecurity industry in Europe, transferring applied R&D in the field to the main industrial sectors. The consortium is composed by 44 partners from 14 countries, and the technological centre Eurecat is one of the participant entities.
- **Impacts:** Delivered cybersecurity self-assessment tools for the automotive sector, helping this key industry in Spain and Europe to adopt advanced security technology and strengthening Europe’s digital sovereignty.

Joint public-private industrial collaboration initiatives

- **Description:** GMV has launched successful joint R&D initiatives with universities and research centres, guaranteeing an early alignment of objectives among stakeholders to assure the market deployment of new developments. The company has also participated in the INCIBE's Public Procurement of Innovation program.
- **Impacts:** Enabled operational deployment of early-threat-detection platforms and specialized threat-intelligence solutions, integrating R&D results into real cybersecurity environments.

SOCME and DearNeuron projects

- **Description:** R&D projects led by SIRT under INCIBE's Public Procurement of Innovation program, with the objective to translate research in the cybersecurity field into practical cybersecurity solutions to respond to national demand needs.
- **Impacts:** The SOCME project delivered a security operations centre (SOC) tool for SMEs, and the DearNeuron project delivered a platform for citizen data governance and consent, translating research into practical cybersecurity solutions. A third project under the same funding scheme, called *Custodia Encadenada*, is currently under development.

EACTDA (European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association)

- **Description:** Association that promotes the adoption of R&D outputs by Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs). It counts with the participation of three Spanish organisations: the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC), the Spanish Ministry of the Interior and Vicomtech.
- **Impacts:** It facilitates the use of high-TRL cybersecurity solutions in LEAs across Europe, ensuring that advanced research technologies are effectively deployed in operational environments. The "Tools4LEAs" is one of its successful initiatives, facilitating the transfer of research software from EU projects into operational tools.

5. Information sharing mechanisms

Information sharing stands as a key element to guarantee cyber resilience at both national and international levels and requires close coordination among the national ecosystem stakeholders. Information sharing encompasses the exchange threat intelligence, incident reporting and coordination among CSIRTs.

This chapter analyses how cybersecurity-related intelligence and best practices are disseminated across the Spanish ecosystem and with third countries, outlining the guiding formal policies and frameworks, as well as the main mechanisms and operation tools used. It also highlights the main challenges Spain faces to ensure an effective information flow, and other informal information-sharing channels.

5.1. Existing national cybersecurity information-sharing policies and frameworks

Spain's national cybersecurity information-sharing landscape is highly shaped by its membership to the European Union (EU) and the adherence to international commitments, such as the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime and NATO cooperation frameworks.

In this context, Spain's information-sharing approach seeks to strengthen the cooperation within the national ecosystem, with a special focus on the cooperation between public and private stakeholders. Indeed, information sharing is a central element to reinforce both national and international resilience in front of cyberthreats.

At the national level, Spain's information-sharing framework is structured around several interconnected legal and strategic policy instruments. These instruments define how information flows among public entities, critical infrastructure operators, and private organisations, setting coordination mechanisms, technical standards and clear responsibilities to ensure a secure exchange on cybersecurity threat data.

Key National Information-Sharing Frameworks

- **National Cybersecurity Strategy:** The National Cybersecurity Strategy (2019) is the principal reference document. Among its objectives, it includes the security and resilience of networks and information systems of the public sector and essential services, the promotion of a safe and reliable use of cyberspace, and the reinforcement of international cooperation. The Strategy outlines the importance of public-private collaboration and real-time and secure information exchange on cybersecurity attacks and threats as fundamental topics for national security.

- **National Security Framework (ENS):** The ENS (2022) establishes the security policy for the use of electronic means by public administrations and their collaborating entities. It requires the implementation of secure exchange channels and standardized processes, developed primarily by CCN-CERT, for sharing incident and vulnerability information. Compliance with these standards is fundamental for effective cyber-incident coordination across public administrations.

- **Legal Mandates:** Law 40/2015 on the Legal Regime of the Public Sector provides the basis framework for secure digital communications. Even though it has no specific cybersecurity-related information sharing mandate, it establishes the general principles to regulate electronic relations and interoperability among the Spanish public administrations, ensuring a secure data exchange and coordination between them.

Furthermore, other legislative documents address specific domains. Two relevant examples are the Law 8/2011 on Critical Infrastructure Protection and the Royal Decree-Las 7/2022 on 5G Network Security. These regulations reinforce the national framework by increasing cybersecurity information-sharing obligations to operators of critical infrastructure and emerging technologies.

These frameworks are strongly aligned with European and international standards. The effective transposition of the NIS Directive, which occurred in 2018, introduced a structured framework for cross-border cybersecurity information exchange and

cooperation among EU member states. It fostered the creation of sectoral CSIRTs, save communication channels and formal incident reporting mechanisms.

Currently, Spain is adapting its legal framework to the NIS2 Directive (EU 2022/2555), which raises the requirements, mandating EU member states to enhance threat intelligence exchange, standardize incident notification processes and ensure interoperability across European countries. The ongoing transposition (through the Preliminary Draft of the Cybersecurity Coordination and Governance Law approved in January 2025) aims to consolidate these new requirements under the new National Cybersecurity Centre, which will become the central point of contact for coordination and information exchange.

Participation in other international frameworks, like the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime, also has a positive impact on information-sharing and cooperation in incident response and cybercrime investigations at a global level.

Evaluation of Information Exchange practices in Spain

Spain's legal and institutional structures for cybersecurity information sharing are comprehensive and aligned with international standards. However, practical implementation faces several barriers. The most significant challenge is the limited trust between public authorities and the private stakeholders, undermining the voluntary exchange of threat and incident information.

In this context, private organisations are often reluctant to share threat and incident information, due to concerns of reputational damage and potential legal sanctions. Moreover, the outsourcing of some operational services by public institutions to private third parties also prevent information sharing, as private stakeholders consider their competitors could access their sensitive information.

Another important point is the complex bureaucracy. Overlapping legal regimes, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), introduces additional and complex

compliance requirements that can delay or even restrict the exchange of cybersecurity information, especially when personal data is involved.

To overcome these bottlenecks, experts stress the importance of promoting trust-building initiatives, the standardization of protocols and incentives mechanisms in order to foster mutual confidence among the public and the private sectors and strengthen information flow within the Spanish cybersecurity ecosystem.

5.2. Cybersecurity threat intelligence sharing mechanisms, platforms and tools

Spain articulates its cybersecurity information-sharing system through a multi-stakeholder approach, with a predominant role of public organisms. The core structure for incident response and information sharing lies on a network of Computer Emergency Response Teams (CERTs/CSIRTs) and specialized collaborative networks.

In the information-sharing domain, Spain operates a Dual National CERT System, comprising the two main national CERTs, CCN-CERT and INCIBE-CERT. This particularity differentiates the Spanish model from other European countries that typically maintain just one single national CERT. In fact, Spain hosts a broad network of regional and sectoral CSIRTs, and it is one of the European countries with the highest number of operational CERTs.

On one hand, the CCN-CERT activity focuses on public administration, coordinating the national technical response to cyberattacks. Operating under the National Intelligence Centre (CNI), the CCN-CERT monitors the cybersecurity of public sector networks and systems, granting it direct access to information and data on ongoing cyberattacks, including classified sources.

On the other hand, INCIBE-CERT serves as the main contact point for citizens, professionals, companies (especially SMEs), and essential services operators. It largely

relies on information voluntarily shared by companies and on cooperation with the CCN-CERT and other regional and sectoral CSIRTs.

The Joint Cyber Space Command (MCCE) supervises the ESPDEF-CERT, the defence sector's CERT. Through ESPDEF-CERT, it complements the work of CCN-CERT and INCIBE-CERT by facilitating information sharing within the national defence domain.

Building upon this institutional framework, Spain has developed a series of collaborative and coordination mechanisms to strengthen the exchange of cybersecurity information and cooperation among the national stakeholders:

- **National SOC (Security Operations Centre) Network:** Promoted by the CCN-CERT, this network integrates public and private Security Operations Centres (SOCs) to share information on cyber threats. The network aims to encourage entities that receive the initial cyberattack to share information with the rest of the ecosystem to coordinate responses.

- **Sectoral CERTs and ISACs:** Specialized CERTs and ISACs for specific industries (like finance, energy or telecommunications) to enable a more tailored approach to threat intelligence sharing. However, coordination between these sectoral networks and the primary national CERTs has room for improvement.

- **National Cybersecurity Forum (FNC):** Established in 2020, this body acts as a superstructural node coordinated by the National Security Department (DSN), INCIBE, and CCN. Its main objective is to promote public-private collaboration, placing information exchange as one of its top priorities.

Main Tools and Technologies

To support threat intelligence dissemination and processing, Spanish stakeholders utilize various technical tools, platforms, and standards:

- **Intelligence Platforms:** National organisations integrate platforms such as MISP (Malware Information Sharing Platform), OpenCTI, and other commercial threat intelligence platforms into their SOC and CERT environments. MISP, an open-source solution, is the most widely used threat intelligence sharing platform in Europe and one of the most internationally recognized.

- **Proprietary Tools:** The CCN-CERT develops and utilizes its own tools, such as LUCIA, a system to monitor infrastructures to detect and alert on potential security anomalies, and PILAR, a risk assessment tool aligned with the National Security Framework. INCIBE also operates platforms like ICARO, designed to promote the distribution of cyber security threat information.

- **Standards:** Spain aligns with international standards like Trusted Automated Exchange of Indicator Information (TAXII) and Structured Threat Information Expression (STIX) to standardize and automate information sharing. These standards improve the speed and efficiency of information dissemination during cyber incidents.

These operational mechanisms and platforms have generally proven effective in coordinating and managing major incidents. The active participation in the National SOC Network, which is rewarded by levels of recognition (Gold and Silver) based on the volume of information shared, enhances coordinated response.

Furthermore, informal cybersecurity information sharing channels, through professional forums, sectoral associations, and trusted networks, plays a key role in detecting emerging threats and providing early alerts, complementing formal channels and helping to build trust.

However, the effectiveness and efficiency of cybersecurity information sharing face multiple challenges:

- **Granularity and Speed:** Although information sharing is frequent, the level of detail and timelines of the shared information has room for improvement. Information sharing often relies on personal relationships of trust, which makes the system inconsistent.
- **Lack of a Single Point of Reference:** The system is fragmented across multiple public actors (CCN, INCIBE, MCCE, CNPIC and regional centres), and there is no clear one-stop window for cyberthreat information dissemination. This lack of clarity affects especially SMEs, which struggle to identify where they can access the relevant intelligence information.
- **Trust and Reputational Concerns:** Despite the consolidated frameworks, the underlying reluctance of organisations to share data due to reputational and financial costs, as well as confidentiality concerns, remains a major challenge.
- **Technical and Maturity Heterogeneity:** Differences in technical capabilities, implementation of standards, legal obligations and cybersecurity intelligence maturity across sectors, persisting even with the adoption of standards like TAXII and STIX, limit the cybersecurity information sharing. For example, in R&D projects involving organisations from critical sectors, the exchange of sensitive information is limited by legal obligations, constraining data-sharing and collaboration.

5.3. International cooperation and best practices in cybersecurity information sharing

International cooperation is a key element of Spain's approach to cybersecurity information sharing. By engaging in European and global alliances, Spain strengthens its capacity to exchange threat intelligence, improve situational awareness and promotes both technical and process interoperability among national and international stakeholders.

Spain's international engagement is structured across European, transatlantic, and bilateral levels, reflecting its commitment to collective security.

European Union (EU) Framework

Spain is adhered to the EU regulations, including the EU Cybersecurity Act and the NIS Directive, as well as its updated version NIS2, currently in the transposition phase to the national legal framework. Key cooperative entities and programs include:

- **ENISA (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity):** Spain actively participates in ENISA initiatives and collaborates with other EU member states in the exchange of cybersecurity threat intelligence.
- **European CSIRTs Network:** Spain participates in this essential coordination mechanism through its two national-level CERTs: the CCN-CERT and INCIBE-CERT.
- **European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC):** Spain has a presence in the ECCC, with INCIBE acting as the National Coordination Centre to link national and EU-level activities, including information sharing.
- **Defence-related Cooperation:** Spain engages in European defence-related initiatives through the European Defence Agency (EDA) and the European Defence Fund (EDF), in project focused on secure communication and information-sharing infrastructures in the defence sector.

International Alliances and Bilateral Agreements

Spain's cooperation with transatlantic partners reinforces its integration into broader information-sharing frameworks. As an active member of NATO, Spain participates in exercises like Cyber Coalition and Locked Shields, that promote intelligence sharing and operational coordination. NATO's Malware Information Sharing Platform (MISP) enables Spanish CERTs and defence bodies to exchange information with other NATO members in near real time.

At the global level, Spain ratified the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime in 2010, guiding Spain's cross-border information sharing to fight cybercrime. At the same time, Spain is an active participant in the Forum of Incident Response and Security Teams (FIRST), a

trusted international community that fosters cross-border cybersecurity information sharing among incident response stakeholders.

In parallel, Spain has bilateral agreements with third countries. Among them, the four-year collaboration agreement between INCIBE and Japan (through its CERT, JPCERT/CC), signed in 2024, is the only Memorandum of Understanding that explicitly focuses on the exchange of information on cybersecurity incidents.

Impact of International Cooperation in Cybersecurity Information Sharing

Even though international cooperation in cybersecurity information sharing has a significant positive impact on Spain, aligning national practices with global standards and increasing the country's cyber resilience, it faces several challenges that must be addressed:

- **Talent Shortage:** The lack of cybersecurity threat intelligence specialists in Spain, and the high reliance on personal trust networks limits the country's capacity to engage in large-scale cybersecurity information sharing networks and frameworks.
- **Sovereignty and Harmonization:** Persistent challenges remain concerning data sovereignty and the need for a greater regulatory harmonization across countries, which can affect the flow of cross-border cybersecurity threat information.
- **Legal Constraints and Bureaucracy:** Translating European directives into national law can be slow, and national legislations that restrict the sharing of sensitive information can prevent a deeper exchange of information, especially in R&D and defence-related contexts.

5.4. Challenges in cross-sectoral information sharing

While Spain has a robust multi-stakeholder governance model and has established several frameworks for cybersecurity information sharing, there are still significant barriers that constraint the effective and timely exchange of cybersecurity information between national stakeholders. These challenges mainly lay around issues of trust, legal complexity, and technical heterogeneity.

Lack of Trust between the public and private sectors

The primary barrier is the prevalent lack of trust among stakeholders, especially between the public and private agents. Private companies are often reluctant to share sensitive information regarding vulnerabilities and attacks due to fears of reputational damage and potential economic loss. In this regard, the tendency to blame the victim, combined with the risk of high financial penalties under new and future regulations like NIS2, discourages private companies even more from reporting incidents or sharing vulnerabilities with government entities.

Moreover, trust is undermined when public institutions are perceived as slow in incidence response and support, or when they maintain relationships with other competitor companies. In some cases, the outsourcing of critical cybersecurity functions to specific third parties, due to limited public resources, creates concerns among other stakeholders, who may hesitate to share sensitive data with potential competitors.

The lack of trust leads to isolated defence mechanisms, hindering timely information exchange and weakening the national response to cyber threats. When private actors withhold sensitive data, they limit the creation of a reliable proactive intelligence mechanism that could prevent the other stakeholders in the early stages of the cybersecurity incidents. Consequently, the public response is often reactive, managing incidents only after they escalate or affect critical infrastructures.

Legal and Regulatory Constraints

Legal frameworks designed for data protection, while protecting citizens privacy, often impede the rapid information sharing necessary for cybersecurity intelligence.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2018) imposes strict limits on the sharing of personal and sensitive information, complicating and delaying the exchange of certain types of information. Organisations frequently struggle with how to detail sensitive information involving clients or third parties due to these privacy concerns.

Intellectual property rights further complicate collaboration, particularly between industry and academia. Sharing confidential information is challenging when R&D projects involve companies from critical sectors. due to the sensitivity of the data and legal obligations.

Moreover, the absence of a single contact point of reference complicates the process, especially for SMEs seeking information or willing to report incidents.

Technical and Cultural Incompatibilities

Technical heterogeneity and organisational maturity disparities among stakeholders complicate the standardization of information sharing mechanisms and procedures.

Sectors and organisations rely on diverse cybersecurity tools, which generate interoperability gaps. While standards like STIX and TAXII help to automate information sharing, implementation remains uneven, limiting the true interoperability across the national ecosystem.

Furthermore, beyond technical issues, there is a lack of cybersecurity awareness and culture across sectors, particularly within SMEs, which represent 99.8% of the business ecosystem of the country. Local administrations often face similar limitations, which weakens national information-sharing initiatives.

In fact, SMEs remain largely excluded from formal information-sharing networks due to their limited technical capacity and the absence of mechanisms to incentivize their

participation in the collaborative frameworks. As a result, an important portion of national SMEs remain vulnerable in front of cybersecurity threats.

5.5. Other informal information and knowledge sharing instruments

Beyond formal information-sharing mechanisms, such as national CERTs, informal channels play a crucial role in underpinning cybersecurity information sharing in Spain, contributing to bridge gaps that the formal structures cannot always address. Then, they must be seen as complementary instruments to the formal structures.

Informal information sharing involves voluntary exchanges outside established legal and bureaucratic protocols, which allows for a faster and more flexible dissemination of threat intelligence. Experts noted that cybersecurity stakeholders are often more confident in exchanging information informally among similar organisations, or actors that already share a pre-existing trusted relationship, than through strictly formal channels.

Cybersecurity professionals utilize diverse non-official channels, including:

- **Trusted Networks and Groups:** These are usually composed of close professional colleagues, sometimes organized into sectoral associations or specialized circles of trust, where they exchange real-time intelligence. A good example is encrypted messaging groups among CISOs from specific sectors, such as banking, energy or telecommunications.
- **Professional Forums and Conferences:** Physical events like national-level or sectoral congresses create spaces where practitioners can share experiences and discuss vulnerabilities with other agents of the ecosystem. The National Cybersecurity Forum (FNC), although being a formal initiative, is an enabler of these informal information sharing spaces.

- **Academic and R&D Networks:** Networks like RENIC (the Spanish Network of Excellence on Cybersecurity Research) foster collaboration and knowledge sharing between universities, research centres and industry, facilitating early-stage cybersecurity information exchange among them.

Despite their benefits, informal channels present several risks that must be managed. On one hand, they often lack the security measures necessary to protect sensitive data, as well as robust verification processes, increasing the risk of spreading misinformation or unverified intelligence.

On the other hand, the depth of information exchanged informally is often limited by confidentiality concerns and privacy restrictions, particularly when sensitive third-party data is involved. This prevents the level of detail necessary for an effective threat analysis and response.

To maximize the value of informal information sharing mechanisms, taking advantage of their agility while mitigating its risks, it is necessary to integrate them into the formal structures.

Spain's cybersecurity framework provides a pathway for this integration, particularly through superstructural nodes like the National Cybersecurity Forum (FNC). The FNC, coordinated by the DSN, INCIBE, and CCN, serves as a bridge between informal collaboration spaces and structured national initiatives, institutionalizing a platform where public and private actors can systematize collaboration and foster a collective cybersecurity culture.

6. Analysis of dual-use technologies

This section explores the intersection between cybersecurity technologies that have applications in both civilian and defence contexts. It discusses the implications of dual-use technologies for national security, innovation, and regulatory compliance.

6.1. Definition and importance of dual-use cybersecurity technologies

In the context of cybersecurity, dual-use technologies are defined as those technologies, knowledge, or developments that can be applied in both civilian and defence spheres. They are utilized in commercial and civil activities as well as in the national security domain. Threats targeting civil infrastructure often employ similar methods to those used against defence systems, which implies that most cybersecurity technologies are inherently dual-use.

Examples of dual-use cybersecurity technologies include cyber intelligence and simulation platforms; AI applications for threat detection, prevention and automated response; encryption and cryptography technologies, designed to secure private data, financial transactions or protect classified military communications; and critical infrastructure management systems.

While the underlying technology is often the same, defence applications require higher reliability and resilience in aggressive environments, while civil uses focus on market scalability and cost efficiency.

Dual-use cybersecurity technologies are fundamental for the economic development of Spain, balancing innovation with national security requirements. International organisations such as NATO and the European Union are placing increasing value on dual-use technologies, backed by significant funding to promote their development and transfer.

Fostering the deployment of domestic dual-use cybersecurity solutions reduce the external technological dependence of Spain, particularly on non-European countries such as Israel or USA, contributing to the strategic autonomy of the EU. Moreover, they enhance the operational capability of military forces, which is crucial in the era of hybrid warfare and cyber-attacks, improving Spain's resilience.

In parallel, by integrating civilian innovations into military applications (spin-in), the defence sector saves R&D costs and exploits available technologies at a lower cost due to the economies of scale of civilian cybersecurity solutions. This synergy fosters industrial competitiveness and economic growth. Additionally, the dual-use approach allows SMEs in the cybersecurity field to access and participate in defence-related innovation projects, fostering their growth and enabling them to be at the vanguard of innovation.

The main benefits of promoting dual-use cybersecurity technologies in Spain are that they enable an efficient reuse of R&D investments and a rapid adaptation of solutions across both sectors. This approach enhances the overall efficiency of cybersecurity technology development, accelerating the time-to-market for innovative solutions and increasing the national industrial base.

Nevertheless, the dual nature of these technologies introduces significant risks, mainly related to control and ethics. If they are not adequately regulated, dual-use technologies could be acquired by malicious actors.

Beyond export regulations, the development and management of dual-use technologies also require a rigorous ethical approach. For instance, the use of AI, which often involves citizens' data, in these types of technologies presents a clear ethical challenge. Regulatory frameworks like the AI Act and the Cyber Resilience act try to address these underlying ethical issues.

6.2. National policies and frameworks governing dual-use cybersecurity solutions

The policy frameworks governing Dual-Use Cybersecurity Technologies in Spain are primarily structured to manage the export and international transfer of sensitive technologies and promote the development of national industry and strategic autonomy. These frameworks aim to enhance both national security capabilities and technological innovation.

National Laws, Regulations, and Policies

The regulatory landscape for dual-use technologies in Spain is highly influenced by international and European mandates. Cybersecurity technologies, by their nature, are intrinsically linked to dual-use applications, so the legal focus tends to be on controlling their export and dissemination, but also in regulating their domestic development.

Export Control and External Trade Regulation

The fundamental European governance mechanism is the EU Dual-Use Export Control Regulation. This framework controls the export, brokering, transit, and transfer (including intangible transfers like emails and cloud data) of dual-use items and technologies. Spanish legislation is bound by this regulation, specially by its 2021 update (EU Regulation 2021/821). The 2021 update strengthens the previous regulatory development by expanding the scope and cooperation between member states and the European Commission, introducing specific controls for cybersurveillance technologies that could be used for internal repression or human-rights violation, creating clearer EU-wide general export authorizations, placing specific obligations on exporters (such as end-use and end-user information), and enabling faster updates of the EU export control list via delegated acts, to respond to the fast evolving security threats and technologies.

The national implementation of the EU Dual-Use Export Control Regulation is through Law 53/2007 on the Control of Foreign Trade in Defence Material, other Material, and Dual-Use Products and Technologies, which regulates the control of external trade in defence and dual-use material.

The licensing process for exporting dual-use goods is supervised by the Interministerial Board for Trade in Defence and Dual-Use Goods, functionally attached to the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Enterprise, under the presidency of the Secretary of State of Trade. The Ministry of Defence is part of it, through some of its bodies like the Directorate General of Armament and Material and the National Intelligence Centre (CNI).

Furthermore, the Spanish government, through the General Subdirectorate for International Trade in Defence and Dual-Use Material, is responsible of issuing export licenses and providing regulatory guidance to ensure compliance with national laws and international regulations.

Policies for Dual-use Technology Promotion

While export controls are crucial in risk mitigation, various national defence and innovation policies promote the development of dual-use cybersecurity technologies:

Dual-use technologies are an important part of the Spanish defence framework. The Ministry of Defence, through the National Defence Directive (2020), emphasizes the technological and industrial base in defence, providing scope for dual-use innovation. On the other hand, Defence Policy Directive (2020) establishes the criterion to strengthen the industrial defence base, facilitating dual-use innovation in coordination with other ministries to mitigate external technological dependence.

The Spanish government supports the cybersecurity and defence industrial base through the Industrial and Technological Plan for Security and Defence, approved in April 2025, which allocates a total investment of 10,471 million euros, which includes a 1,157 million euros investment plan to develop cybersecurity technologies.

On the other hand, Institutions like the CDTI utilize funding instruments such as Misiones, Cervera and Neotec to support R&D projects explicitly targeting dual-use technologies. Finally, the COINCIDENTE program, managed by the General Directorate of Armament and Material (Ministry of Defence), supports the integration and transfer of civilian technologies into defence capabilities.

General Regulatory Frameworks

General legislation intended primarily for civil security also impacts on dual-use cybersecurity technologies. The National Security Framework (ENS), updated by Royal Decree 311/2022, establishes compliance mechanisms for public administrations. The

CCN-CERT manages the catalogue of certified STIC products, ensuring that technologies developed for the public sector meet rigorous security requirements, facilitating their potential application in defence contexts.

In parallel, the ongoing transposition of the NIS2 Directive (through the Cybersecurity Coordination and Governance Law) expands security obligations and coordination across essential and critical entities. This increased regulatory demand inherently promotes the adoption of high-standard security technologies, many of which are dual-use, facilitating their subsequent application in defence settings.

Alignment with International Standards and Best Practices

Spain's framework is broadly aligned with European and international mandates, in concordance with its EU membership and global commitments.

Spain actively participates in EU programs (such as Horizon Europe) and is committed to the goal of standardizing cybersecurity models across Europe, which facilitates cross-border cooperation and dual-use technology promotion. The national legal framework is aligned with European standards such as the EU Cybersecurity Act.

Spain is also involved in global export controls initiatives. In this area, Spain is a participant state of the Wassenaar Arrangement (1996), a multilateral export control regime that sets guidelines for the international trade of dual-use goods and technologies, including cyber surveillance tools. National export licensing and control mechanisms in Spain draw on the principles established under the Arrangement, and these principles inform the work of the Interministerial Board for Trade in Defence and Dual-Use Goods

Finally, through its membership of NATO and EU, Spain engages in cyber-defence cooperative initiatives, in areas like capability sharing, interoperability frameworks and security clearance protocols. These mechanisms support the secure development, transfer and integration of dual-use technologies among allied states.

6.3. Challenges in regulating and managing dual-use technologies

Although the Spanish regulatory framework is effective in controlling dual-use technology exports, it faces several challenges in facilitating the development and adoption of dual-use cybersecurity technologies. In fact, achieving effective supervision and management of dual-use cybersecurity technologies is constrained by structural gaps, mainly due to the lack of a comprehensive strategic framework, the regulatory environment, ethical considerations, and the rapid pace of technological development.

Strategic and policymaking gaps

Lack of a Comprehensive Dual-Use Cybersecurity Technology Strategy in Spain

A key issue in the development of dual-use cybersecurity technologies in Spain is the lack of a clear industrial policy specifically supporting technologies that serve both civilian and defence purposes. While Spain has recognized the importance of dual use technologies through initiatives like the Industrial and Technological Plan for Security and Defence, a fully coordinated national strategy is still lacking.

Spanish policies in the field focus mainly on export controls and do not fully cover the entire lifecycle of dual use technologies, including R&D, commercialization, and adaptation from civilian to military use. As a result, some areas face unclear regulations, limiting the growth of domestic dual-use industrial capabilities.

Legislation lags behind technology

A core constraint is that legislation evolves more slowly than technology, which is particularly problematic in the rapidly evolving technological domain of cybersecurity. In consequence, dual-use technology developers operate under outdated legal frameworks. This legislative lag can restrict the development and adaptation of cutting-edge cybersecurity technologies for both the civil and the defence spheres.

Regulatory and Bureaucratic Constraints

Over-regulation and Rigidity

Although the European Commission (EC) generally promotes flexible directives, their transposition and implementation at the national level frequently results in "over-regulation". Experts note that overly strict criteria create important barriers to business continuity, discouraging investment and slowing the development pace of dual-use technologies.

In addition, regulations on cross-border transfer of dual-use technologies and the commercial exploitation of publicly funded R&D are often too rigid, undermining the development and scalability of these technologies.

Administrative Bottlenecks and Fragmentation

Private companies, particularly SMEs, face excessive bureaucracy when applying to funding programs or mandatory certifications. The bureaucratic slowness in implementing specific programs has been noted as a significant difficulty by cybersecurity companies when they want to develop new technologies.

Furthermore, national standards and certifications can become an additional barrier when their pace lags behind international and European benchmarks. This lagging pace can prevent the use of technologies that already comply with current European and international standards due to pending national certification processes.

This fragmentation, together with a lack of clarity on processes and the difficulties identifying a central national point of reference when companies seek information, weaken the development of domestic dual-use cybersecurity technologies. Similar bottlenecks arise in the national-level homologation and certification of civil technologies for defence applications. Lengthy bureaucratic processes prevent the timely deployment of technologies across both the civil and defence domains.

Intellectual Property Rights Restrictions

The management of intellectual property rights, especially when dual-use technology is developed with public funds or in partnership with public entities like universities or research foundations, further complicates technology transfer. Companies collaborating with Public Administrations face patent and transfer rules that could restrict commercialization and the cross-sector deployment of dual-use cybersecurity technologies. There is a desire among experts for greater clarity and flexibility regarding the commercial exploitation of R&D results stemming from public programs.

This is particularly challenging in mixed-funding scenarios where both public and private resources contribute to the development of dual-use technologies. Universities and public research organisations, strictly committed to intellectual property right protection protocols, can unintentionally slow or block the transfer of technology to the market and from civil use to defence applications. Defence stakeholders often cite these restrictions as barriers to the rapid transfer of dual-use cybersecurity technologies between the civil and defence sectors.

Ethical Considerations

The development of dual-use cybersecurity technologies demands a robust ethical and governance framework. Almost any modern cybersecurity tool can be used for both defence and offense. For instance, Artificial Intelligence applications can be used for phishing campaigns. For this reason, dual-use cybersecurity technology developers and public administrations must exercise extreme caution and impose necessary safeguards and controls to prevent misuse of their solutions.

Ethical concerns intensify when military surveillance tools are adapted for civilian use, creating potential conflicts between national security objectives and individual privacy rights. Beyond legal compliance, organisations involved in dual-use technological development often face internal ethical challenges, questioning their values regarding where their technology should be deployed.

Technological Complexities

The rapidly evolving landscape of cyber threats presents several technical difficulties for dual-use technologies regulation and management. The widespread adoption of AI has exponentially increased both the volume and sophistication of cyber threats. AI also increases the number of alerts that must be addressed and accelerates the pace of attacks, raising the risk that human operators may lose control. Nevertheless, fully delegation of cyber defence to automated systems remains unfeasible.

At the same time, the rapid evolution of technologies makes it increasingly difficult to clearly distinguish between purely civilian and defence applications, leading to regulatory grey areas where the scope and application of technologies are ambiguous, complicating supervision, certification and compliance.

Another key technological complexity is the adaptation of technologies across sectors. Although many civil technologies have applications in the military domain, their technical adaptation is often complex. The more specialized the operational field, the greater modifications the tool requires, representing a significant technical barrier to dual-use cybersecurity technologies deployment.

Export controls and International Cooperation Barriers

Strict Export Controls

Dual-use technologies are subject to strict regulations concerning their exports, under frameworks such as the Regulation (EU) 2021/821. The primary goal of these regulations is to prevent sensitive technologies from being acquired by third parties who may misuse them. This regulation lists various items, including intangible transfers such as software or technical data.

Despite these frameworks are effective in fulfilling their goal, the slow administrative licensing process represents an important barrier, especially for SMEs. Obtaining an export license can take 9 to 10 months, which can result in the loss of international clients. This bureaucratic complexity hampers the integration of domestic dual-use technologies into the global cybersecurity market.

Conversely, while exports are heavily controlled, import controls for dual-use technologies are limited, creating potential risks if sensitive tools are acquired by malicious actors.

International Cooperation Challenges

International collaboration is key for the development of dual-use cybersecurity technologies, providing access to joint innovation projects and coordinated defence capabilities. However, it faces challenges due to the lack of harmonisation across different countries. Divergent national legislations regulating defence applications, export control regimes and certification requirements complicate the cross-border development and deployment of dual-use cybersecurity technologies, slowing the joint adoption of dual-use technologies at the European level.

At the same time, dual-use cybersecurity R&D projects often involve sensitive data. Different requirements for data storage, processing, and transfer across countries are a persistent obstacle for cross-border collaboration in dual-use cybersecurity technology development projects.

Impact on National Security and Innovation

Regulatory and management challenges in the dual-use cybersecurity sector have direct and significant implications for both industrial innovation and national security.

Impact on Innovation

The lack of clear regulation and a defined industrial policy for dual-use technologies generates legal uncertainty for the private sector. Companies face the risk that technologies they develop may later be restricted for export or deployment in defence contexts. This uncertainty discourages SMEs from pursuing riskier, high-impact innovation projects, while larger companies tend to focus on safer, low-risk innovations.

Additionally, bureaucratic burdens, restrictive intellectual property rules on publicly funded research, and difficulties in scaling technologies from research to operational environments further slow the commercialization of dual-use R&D results. Together, these

factors slow innovation and reduce the international competitiveness of domestic companies in the cybersecurity sector.

Impact on National Security

The absence of clear and coherent regulatory frameworks, together with a weak domestic market for dual-use cybersecurity technologies, undermines Spain's strategic autonomy. Excessive national regulations and restrictions on the commercial exploitation of publicly funded R&D create barriers that hinder innovation and perpetuate reliance on foreign technology providers.

In parallel, mismanagement or inadequate regulation of dual-use technologies can also create security vulnerabilities. Sensitive tools may fall into the wrong hands, or their deployment may compromise ethical standards, threatening national interests. Ensuring that dual-use innovations are developed, scaled, and deployed responsibly is therefore critical to balance both industrial competitiveness and national security resilience.

6.4. Examples of cybersecurity technologies with dual-use applications

Domestic innovation in cybersecurity, for its inherent nature, shows a strong dual-use potential in Spain, with several national and European projects serving as good practices for how civilian technologies can be adapted to defence needs, and vice versa. It proves that investment in R&D not only strengthens the Spanish industrial ecosystem but also develops interoperable and scalable solutions that address both civilian and defence needs.

Cyber intelligence, data analytics and AI applications

These technologies are highly dual-use because both civil and defence stakeholders face similar threat models and require the ability to analyse large and heterogeneous datasets in a fast pace.

Technology: AI for hybrid threat defence

- **Application/Project:** fAIr (INCIBE Public Procurement of Innovation Program).
- **Developer/Coordinator:** GRADIANT
- **Description:** fAIr is a platform that leverages multimodal Artificial Intelligence (AI) to detect and counter threats arising from the malicious use of generative AI. Through advanced multimedia content analysis techniques, fAIr detects whether images, videos, or audio recordings have been generated or manipulated using AI, enabling a fast and effective response to digital fraud attempts such as deepfakes or synthetic documents.
- **Outcomes and Impacts:** This technology reinforces trust, security, and integrity in digital environments. In the defence sphere, it helps the early detection and characterization of disinformation campaigns directed against national interests, while also addressing fraud detection and protection in the civil sector. These technologies are highly dual-use because both civil and defence stakeholders face similar threat models and require the ability to analyse large and heterogeneous datasets in a fast pace.

Technology: UEBA for social media and dark web monitoring

- **Application/Project:** PRESERVE (Horizon Europe).
- **Developer/Coordinator:** GRADIANT
- **Description:** The project applies state-of-the-art AI and privacy-enhancing technologies to support real-time criminal investigations in collaboration with European Law Enforcement Authorities (LEAs). The project develops and integrates User and Entity Behaviour Analytics (UEBA) to detect and anticipate criminal and terrorist behaviour through large-scale behavioural pattern analysis.
- **Outcomes and Impacts:** The use of Federated Learning enables collaborative intelligence across European LEAs without transferring sensitive data, ensuring a secure cooperation while combating threats like terrorism or organized crime. In the civil sphere, it is applied to areas such as fraud detection or urban mobility.

Technology: Cyber intelligence platforms and toolsets

- **Application/Project:** Cyber intelligence platforms and cyber-defence simulation & training environments
- **Developer/Coordinator:** GMV
- **Description:** GMV develops advanced platforms for cyber intelligence and cyber-defence simulation that support scenario-based training, threat hunting, and high-fidelity emulation of cyberattack conditions, to promote capability development and cybersecurity resilience in national security environments.

- **Application/Project:** ASGARD (Horizon 2020)
- **Developer/Coordinator:** Vicomtech
- **Description:** This project developed a cutting-edge tool set for analysing and extracting big data for Law Enforcement Agencies, facilitating forensic investigations. Technology is transferred to end users under an open-source scheme focusing on forensics, intelligence and foresight.
- **Application/Project:** TITANIUM (Horizon 2020)
- **Developer/Coordinator:** Vicomtech
- **Description:** This project developed and validated novel data-driven techniques and solutions designed to support Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) charged with investigating criminal or terrorist activities involving virtual currencies or underground markets in the darknet.

- **Outcomes and Impacts:** These solutions enable effective investigation of complex cybercrime (ransomware, identity-theft, etc.) while also supporting realistic training and threat-hunting operations, enhancing both the national cyber-defence readiness and the resilience of private companies and operators of critical infrastructure.

Resilience and critical infrastructure systems

The dual-use application of these technologies is driven by the shared requirement for high levels of resilience, security and operational control across geographically dispersed systems, whether they are civilian infrastructure or military networks.

Technology: Edge-to-cloud Mesh architecture

- **Application/Project:** SELFY (Horizon Europe).
- **Developer/Coordinator:** Eurecat Technology Centre
- **Description:** SELFY combines edge-to-cloud computing with the principles of Mesh architecture to create a distributed, dynamic and resilience cybersecurity architecture. It promotes automated defence systems, capable of operating without human intervention, even in scenarios of subsystem disruptions or isolation.
- **Outcomes and Impacts:** This technology promotes national resilience, securing civil critical infrastructures like smart grids or digital health, while also supporting defence applications in areas like battlefield networks.

Technology: Secure hybrid connectivity and management

- **Application/Project:** Comprehensive and Secure Connectivity Network
Developer/Coordinator: OVERON
Description: An advanced and secure connectivity network integrating LEO satellites and cloud-based infrastructure to enable real-time video transmission in remote locations across critical water infrastructure.
- **Application/Project:** Global Video Management System – VMS Milestone Systems
- **Developer/Coordinator:** SETESUR
- **Description:** A unified management system that centralizes various network devices of critical infrastructures, such as the Sierra Nevada ski resort, including cameras, communications, access controls, and related hardware. The system allows to enforce security policies and integrates operation oversight.

- **Outcomes and Impacts:** These technologies, applied in civilian settings, have a set of capacities (such as remote management or data centralisation) that can be extrapolated to military applications, such as command-and-control tasks. They open the door to the participation of SMEs with proven dual-use cybersecurity solutions in defence-related projects.

Foundational security and cryptography

The dual-use application of these technologies is driven by the fact that fundamental security mechanisms, especially those concerning information protection and digital identity, are essential across all high-stakes environments.

Technology: Foundational Privacy and Identity Technologies

- **Application/Project:** ÉGIDA (CDTI's Cervera program)
- **Developer/Coordinator:** GRADIANT and Vicomtech
- **Description:** ÉGIDA advances research in technologies in the area of applied cryptography (protecting confidential data), digital identity, fraud prevention, and secure distributed systems (IoT, 5G, DLT/blockchain).
- **Outcomes and Impacts:** The project builds national capabilities in emerging strategic low TRL areas such as quantum and post-quantum cryptography and hardware and software cybersecurity, which are essential for securing both classified military communications and civil systems, contributing to the national strategic autonomy.

Technology: Digital Chains of Custody and Citizen-Centric Security Mechanisms

- **Application/Project:** Digital chains of custody and cognitive-defence initiatives.
- **Developer/Coordinator:** SIRT
- **Description:** The company develops digital chain-of-custody technologies that ensure reliable and traceable data provenance throughout the entire data lifecycle. More broadly, it also advances technologies that preserve citizens' data rights and

enable ethical participation in national-defence-related digital environments, including cognitive resilience initiatives.

- **Outcomes and Impacts:** These solutions address fundamental dual-use ethical challenges involving citizens data, which is essential for civil forensic investigations and defence intelligence workflows.

7. Recommendations

This chapter presents fourteen actionable policy recommendations aimed to mitigate the existing bottlenecks that hinder the full development of the Spanish cybersecurity ecosystem. The recommendations are structured across five core areas: governance, technology transfer, information sharing, dual-use cybersecurity technologies management, and capacity building.

7.1 Strengthening national cybersecurity governance

Spain's governance model for cybersecurity remains fragmented, especially at the regional and local level. This fragmentation creates vulnerabilities in national cyber defence and slows the effective deployment of new technological innovations.

- Advance the creation and operational deployment of the National Cybersecurity Centre, as proposed in the Preliminary Draft of the Cybersecurity Coordination and Governance Law. Once created, the NCC should be positioned as the single point of reference to guide the national stakeholders, particularly for SMEs and local administrations, to consolidate the national cybersecurity governance framework. The NCC should also reinforce the coordination among multilevel operation bodies and between the public and the private sectors.
- Integrate and facilitate the transfer of expertise from central operational bodies (such as CCN-CERT and INCIBE) to local and regional administrations, accompanied by the implementation of mandatory technical assistance programs and dedicated funding to ensure all regional and local public administrations comply with the National Security Framework and NIS2. These actions would improve the cyber resilience of public administrations in front of regional and local level cyberattacks.

- Simplify administrative procedures for procurement, funding and certification to accelerate innovation and boost the national industrial development in the cybersecurity field, leveraging programs like INICBE's Public Procurement of Innovation as agile mechanisms to adopt high-TRL domestic cybersecurity technologies. At the same time, it is important to harmonise national certification processes to align with European and international standards and avoid delays in the deployment of new cybersecurity technologies to the national market.

7.2 Enhancing technology transfer mechanisms

Spain's regulatory incentives for technology transfer are strong, but challenges such as the rigid intellectual property frameworks or the preference for foreign technology in the domestic market limits its full potential.

- Ensure legal certainty for private partners participating in publicly funded R&D projects, by establishing transparent and flexible rules for licensing and revenue sharing. These measures would incentivise the active participation of all stakeholders in collaborative R&D initiatives and ensure a successful technology transfer of research outcomes.
- Reinforce and promote demand-driven funding programs such as INCIBE's Public Procurement of Innovation to push the demand for national cybersecurity R&D solutions and introduce fiscal incentives to encourage essential service operators to adopt certified domestic technologies.
- Simplify administrative requirements to promote SMEs participation in technology transfer programs, expanding incubation and acceleration initiatives to better link knowledge and technological centres with SMEs to bridge the gap between high-TRL research and the market.

7.3 Improving information sharing practices

Effective collective intelligence is constrained by public-private trust gaps and complex legal frameworks.

- Develop confidential and legally protected incident reporting channels to mitigate the reputational and financial risks the private companies face when sharing information, as well as to address the potential conflicts of interest arising from public outsourcing to competing private companies.
- Promote a uniform adoption of international threat intelligence standards (such as STIX and TAXII) across sectorial CSIRTs and the National SOC Network, and the establishment of a single early-warning protocol to ensure timely and actionable cyber intelligence for all national stakeholders, especially SMEs.
- Institutionalise, as much as possible, informal professional networks by linking them with formal structures, such as the National Cybersecurity Forum, and establishment of systematisation and validation mechanisms for cyber intelligence gathered from informal channels, to ensure its security and reliability.

7.4 Promoting dual-use cybersecurity technologies

Cybersecurity is an inherent dual-use sector, but the management of this dual-use potential is hampered by regulatory lags and the lack of a comprehensive dual-use industrial policy.

- Develop a long-term industrial policy framework that covers the full lifecycle of dual-use cybersecurity technologies, aligning the efforts of the Ministries of Defence and Science, Innovation and Universities. This strategy should support the spin-in process to boost the adaptation of civilian cybersecurity technologies to defence settings, building upon existing programs such as COINCIDENTE (Ministry of Defence).
- Simplify the administrative procedures to reduce delays in obtaining dual-use cybersecurity technology export licenses, enabling Spanish companies to be competitive in the international markets.
- Develop a flexible governance framework for dual-use innovation to ensure compliance with data protection standards, prevent misuse of dual-use technologies and align their deployment with current and upcoming EU regulations (such as the AI Act).

7.5 Capacity building and awareness

Spain faces a critical shortage of cybersecurity talent, as well as low levels of cyber maturity in the SMEs, which weakens the country's overall resilience in front of cyberthreats.

- Increase public investment in cybersecurity education, both at the university and vocational training levels, to expand the qualified workforce base in cybersecurity, addressing the estimated shortfall of 40,000 specialists by 2024 (INCIBE, last disponible number), which is expected to even increase for the following years. In parallel, use the existing international training platforms to enhance operational capacities in both public and private organisations, and promote gender diversity initiatives to reduce the female representation gap.
- Foster cybersecurity awareness across public administrations, the private sector, and citizens through capacity-building and outreach initiatives such as INCIBE Emprende, CyberCamp and ATENEA, to reduce the dependency of the Spanish organisations on outsourcing cybersecurity operations.

8. Conclusions

This report analyses the Spanish national ecosystem regarding cybersecurity technology and information transfer. The study provides a comprehensive overview of the national cybersecurity and technology transfer regulatory landscape, main actors in the field, information-sharing mechanisms and dual-use technologies governance, as well as a set of preliminary policy recommendations that will be further developed in upcoming tasks of the COcyber project. The findings highlight the strategic commitment of Spain, and identify the structural barriers that compromise the country's cyber resilience and cybersecurity dual-use technologies development and transfer.

On the cybersecurity regulatory side, Spain has developed a mature governance structure, guided by the 2019 National Cybersecurity Strategy and executed through the National Cybersecurity Plan (PNC) 2022–2025. This framework is coordinated by the National Security Council (CSN) and the National Cybersecurity Council (CNC), and operated through the National Cryptologic Centre (CCN), INCIBE, the Joint Cyberspace Command

(MCCE) and the CNPIC. This governance model has positioned Spain among Tier 1 countries in international rankings. However, the study concludes that the implementation of the National Cybersecurity Strategy has been only moderately effective. Persistent structural challenges, including significant institutional fragmentation across regional and local public administrations, a critical talent shortage, low cyber maturity and high dependence on third-party suppliers among SMEs, and a general lack of trust between public and private actors.

Technology transfer is a strategic priority to enhance national security and reduce technological dependence on non-European providers. Spain promotes technology transfer through several institutions and policy instruments, being a notable example INCIBE's Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) program, which has mobilized around 224 million euros to deploy high TRL solutions to respond to demand-driven cybersecurity market needs. However, the rigid administrative procedures and excessive bureaucratic burdens slow down the process and hinder the effective market deployment of high-TRL R&D outputs, especially in the case of SMEs. Other identified barriers are unclear intellectual property rights arrangements in public-private R&D projects, which create legal uncertainty and delay the commercial deployment of new cybersecurity solutions.

Spain has developed a comprehensive structure for cybersecurity information sharing, built around a Dual National CERT System: the CCN-CERT (focused on public administration) and the INCIBE-CERT (focused on citizens and SMEs). Formal collaboration is facilitated through platforms such as the National SOC Network, and the use of technical tools such as MISP (Malware Information Sharing Platform). Despite these frameworks, information sharing remains constrained by the persistent lack of trust among stakeholders. Many private organisations are often reluctant to share sensitive information due to the fear of economic loss and reputational damage. Furthermore, compliance with strict legal regimes, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), introduces technical complexities that can delay or restrict the exchange of certain types of intelligence, especially when personal data might be involved. This combination of

technical and cultural barriers limits the development of a robust collective threat intelligence mechanism at the national level.

Cybersecurity technologies have an inherent dual-use potential, with applications in both the civilian and defence sectors. This duality is essential for strengthening the national strategic autonomy and spin-in civilian innovations into defence contexts. The national and European regulatory framework governing these technologies is primarily centred on export control. While these controls are effective, the management of dual-use technologies is hindered by significant policy gaps, such as the slowness of the export licensing process, which compromises the international competitiveness of domestic companies, and restrictive intellectual property rights conditions in public-funded research, which prevents a rapid transfer of R&D results between the civil and defence spheres.

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10. Annexes

This section includes any additional supporting documents, data, or reference materials that provide further context for the case study.

Annex 1 – In-depth interview questionnaire

Question 1:

From your perspective, how does cybersecurity technology transfer contribute to enhancing national security and resilience in [Country Name]? Could you provide examples of successful initiatives or highlight areas needing improvement?

Purpose:

This open-ended question encourages stakeholders to share detailed insights and specific examples, facilitating a deeper understanding of the practical implications and challenges of cybersecurity technology transfer within the national context.

Question 2:

In your opinion, how effectively the current national cybersecurity strategy has been implemented so far?

Question 3:

Which organisations play a pivotal role in your country's cybersecurity ecosystem, and how do they collaborate to address cybersecurity challenges?

Question 4:

What are the most pressing cybersecurity challenges facing your country, and what measures are being taken to address them?

Question 5:

How does your country engage in international cybersecurity cooperation, and what benefits or challenges have arisen from these partnerships?

Question 6:

How do you define technology transfer in the context of cybersecurity, and why is it important for your organisation or sector?

Question 7:

Can you elaborate on the legal and regulatory frameworks that facilitate or hinder cybersecurity technology transfer in your country?

Question 8:

Which national institutions are most actively involved in cybersecurity technology transfer, and how do they collaborate to facilitate this process?

Question 9:

What are the primary incentives your organisation faces in participating in cybersecurity technology transfer?

Question 10:

What are the primary barriers your organisation faces in participating in cybersecurity technology transfer?

Question 11:

Can you share examples of successful cybersecurity technology transfer initiatives your organisation has been involved in, and what factors contributed to their success?

Question 12:

Can you describe the national policies or frameworks in place for cybersecurity information sharing, and how effectively they function in practice?

Question 13:

Which platforms or tools does your organisation use for sharing and receiving cybersecurity threat intelligence, and how effective are they?

Question 14:

Can you share experiences of international cooperation in cybersecurity information sharing that have benefited your organisation?

Question 15:

What challenges has your organisation faced in sharing cybersecurity information with partners from other sectors?

Question 16:

Does your organisation engage in informal cybersecurity information sharing? If so, through which channels, and how valuable are these interactions?

Question 17:

How does your organisation perceive the role of dual-use cybersecurity technologies in balancing national security and innovation?

Question 18:

Can you elaborate on the national policies or frameworks that regulate dual-use cybersecurity technologies, and how effectively they function in practice?

Question 19:

What challenges has your organisation faced in regulating or managing dual-use cybersecurity technologies?

Question 20:

Can you share examples of cybersecurity technologies with dual-use applications your organisation has developed or utilized, and what factors contributed to their dual-use nature?

Annex 2 – Online survey

Question 1:

Which sector do you represent?

- Public government
- Private sector
- Academic/ research Institution
- Civil society
- Defence-related organisation
- Other (please specify)

Question 2:

Which type of institution do you represent?

- o Government agency
- o Research institution
- o Private sector company
- o Non-Governmental Organisation
- o Defence-related organisation
- o Other (please specify)

Question 3:

On a scale from 1 (Not Important) to 5 (Extremely Important), how important is international collaboration in cybersecurity for your organisation?

Purpose:

This Likert-scale question quantifies the perceived importance of international collaboration, allowing for statistical analysis across different stakeholder groups and countries.

Question 4:

On a scale of 1 (Not Effective) to 5 (Highly Effective), how would you rate the implementation of the national cybersecurity strategy in your country?

Question 5:

Which of the following areas do you consider to be the most significant challenges in your country's cybersecurity landscape? (Select up to three)

- Lack of skilled professionals
- Insufficient funding
- Inadequate legal frameworks Portal
- Poor inter-agency coordination
- Limited public awareness
- Other (please specify)

Question 6:

To what extent does international cooperation enhance your country's cybersecurity capabilities?

- Not at all
- To a small extent
- To a moderate extent
- To a great extent
- To a very great extent

Question 7:

On a scale from 1 (Not Important) to 5 (Extremely Important), how important is technology transfer in advancing cybersecurity capabilities in your country?

Question 8:

How familiar are you with the national legal frameworks governing cybersecurity technology transfer?

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Moderately familiar
- Very familiar
- Extremely familiar

Question 9:

Which of the following factors act as barriers to cybersecurity technology transfer in your country? (Select all that apply)

- Lack of government funding programmes
- Lack of public-private partnerships
- Legal constraints
- Lack of trust among stakeholders
- Insufficient resources
- technical incompatibilities
- Other (please specify)

Question 10:

Are you aware of any successful cybersecurity technology transfer initiatives in your country?

- Yes
- No
- If yes, please provide a brief description:

Question 11:

How familiar are you with your country's cybersecurity information-sharing policies and frameworks?

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Moderately familiar
- Very familiar
- Extremely familiar

Question 12:

Which of the following mechanisms does your organisation utilize for cybersecurity threat intelligence sharing? (Select all that apply)

- National CERT
- ISACs

- Private threat intelligence platforms
- Informal networks
- Other (please specify)

Question 13:

Has your organisation participated in international cybersecurity information-sharing initiatives?

- Yes
- No
- If yes, please specify

Question 14:

Which of the following challenges hinder cross-sectoral cybersecurity information sharing in your experience? (Select all that apply)

- Lack of trust between sectors
- Legal or regulatory barriers
- Technical incompatibilities
- Insufficient resources
- Other (please specify)

Question 15:

Which informal channels does your organisation use for cybersecurity information sharing? (Select all that apply)

- Professional associations
- Industry conferences
- Social media platforms
- Personal networks
- Other (please specify)

Question 16:

On a scale from 1 (Not Important) to 5 (Extremely Important), how important are dual-use cybersecurity technologies to your organisation's operations?

Question 17:

How familiar are you with your country's policies and frameworks governing dual-use cybersecurity technologies?

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Moderately familiar
- Very familiar
- Extremely familiar

Question 18:

Which of the following challenges hinder effective regulation and management of dual-use cybersecurity technologies in your experience? (Select all that apply)

- Legal or regulatory barriers
- Ethical considerations
- Technological complexities
- Lack of international cooperation
- Other (please specify)

Question 19:

Are you aware of any cybersecurity technologies with dual-use applications in your country?"

- Yes
- No
- If yes, please provide a brief description (open answer)

Annex 3 – Questions to guide the National Validation Workshops

Question 1:

Considering the preliminary findings on the national cybersecurity landscape, do you agree with the identified strengths and gaps in technology transfer and information sharing mechanisms? What additional factors or perspectives should be considered to provide a more comprehensive understanding?

Purpose:

This prompt fosters interactive discussion among experts, validating the initial findings and uncovering additional insights or overlooked aspects, thereby enhancing the robustness of the case study.

Question 2:

Based on the preliminary findings, do you agree with the assessment of the national cybersecurity strategy's effectiveness and areas for improvement? What additional insights can you provide?

Question 3:

Are there any key stakeholders or collaborative initiatives in the national cybersecurity landscape that have been overlooked in our preliminary analysis?

Question 4:

Do you concur with the identified challenges and gaps in the national cybersecurity framework? Are there additional issues that should be considered?

Question 5:

Are there specific international partnerships or cooperative efforts that have significantly influenced your country's cybersecurity posture? What lessons can be drawn from these experiences?

Question 6:

Do you agree with the defined concept and importance of technology transfer in cybersecurity as presented? Are there additional aspects or perspectives that should be considered?

Question 7:

Are there any legal or regulatory barriers that significantly impact the effectiveness of technology transfer in your country?

Question 8:

Are there any key institutions or collaborative initiatives in the national cybersecurity technology transfer landscape that have been overlooked in our preliminary analysis?

Question 9:

Do you agree with the identified incentives and barriers to cybersecurity technology transfer? Are there additional factors that should be considered?

Question 10:

Based on our findings, are there additional successful cybersecurity technology transfer initiatives that should be highlighted? What lessons can be drawn from these examples?

Question 11:

Are the current national policies and frameworks sufficient to facilitate effective cybersecurity information sharing? What improvements would you suggest?

Question 12:

Are the current threat intelligence sharing mechanisms and tools adequate for your organisation's needs? What enhancements would you recommend?

Question 13:

What international best practices in cybersecurity information sharing could be adopted or adapted to improve national mechanisms?

Question 14:

What strategies can be implemented to overcome the identified challenges in cross-sectoral information sharing?

Question 15:

How can informal information-sharing practices be integrated or aligned with formal mechanisms to enhance overall cybersecurity resilience?

Question 16:

Do you agree with the defined concept and importance of dual-use cybersecurity technologies as presented? Are there additional aspects or perspectives that should be considered?

Question 17:

Are the current national policies and frameworks sufficient to manage dual-use cybersecurity technologies effectively? What improvements would you suggest?

Question 18:

What strategies can be implemented to overcome the identified challenges in regulating and managing dual-use cybersecurity technologies?

Question 19:

Based on our findings, are there additional cybersecurity technologies with dual-use applications that should be highlighted? What lessons can be drawn from these examples?

Annex 4 – List of stakeholders interviewed

The following organisations took part in interviews (grouped by stakeholder category):

Government agencies and regulators

Centre for Technological Development and Innovation (CDTI)

Ministry of Defence of Spain

National Cybersecurity Institute (INCIBE)

Private sector representatives

GMV

SETESUR

SIRT

Research and academic institutions

Eurecat

Gradient

Vicomtech

Civil society or industry associations

Elcano Royal Institute

Women4Cyber Spain

AMETIC's Cybersecurity Commission

Defence-related organisations

Cooperación Estratégica de Seguridad Nacional (CESN)

Joint Cyberspace Command (MCCE)

AMETIC's Dual-Use Technologies Commission